

Master Thesis on Sound and Music Computing
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MuSA: A New TEL Platform for Enhancing Self-Reflection and Musical Understanding through Saliency Analysis of Performance Recordings

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Abstract

This thesis explores how a technology-enhanced learning (TEL) tool can improve music practice by addressing a critical, often-neglected component of skill development: the reflection phase. It focuses on the development and evaluation of MuSA (Musical Saliency Analyzer), an application designed to provide a pedagogically-grounded platform for analyzing recorded performances to make reflection more efficient and effective. MuSA's design is informed by key educational theories, including the Talent-Development-in-Achievement-Domains (TAD) Music Model and learner-centered teaching (LCT) principles like scaffolding, self-regulated learning (SRL), and self-directed learning (SDL). Its central feature is saliency analysis, which algorithmically identifies key moments in a performance based on variability in musical features such as pitch, dynamics, and tempo. Unlike tools that offer prescriptive, "correct/incorrect" feedback, MuSA encourages a learner's own interpretation. As an accessible, web-based platform, it allows users to upload or record audio for analysis independently of a teacher. To evaluate MuSA's effectiveness, a mixed-methods, within-subjects study was conducted with 14 participants. While the study's small sample size limited statistical power, the findings pointed to several exploratory trends. The data suggested a differential impact based on musical feature and experience level, with dynamics showing the most consistent trend toward objective and perceived improvement. The analysis also suggested a potential expertise reversal effect, where trends showed intermediate musicians gaining from the feedback while advanced musicians experienced neutral or slightly negative changes. Furthermore, the study's self-awareness metrics indicated a general misalignment between participants' self-ratings and objective performance, highlighting a core challenge in the self-reflection phase of independent practice. In conclusion, MuSA offers a potential contribution to TEL for music by leveraging computational analysis to provide targeted insights that can scaffold the reflective process. Although the quantitative results were inconclusive, positive qualitative feedback validates the demand for such a tool. This work provides a functional prototype and a research infrastructure for collecting labeled recording data, demonstrating the dual role of

MuSA as both a learning support system and a potential research tool.

Keywords: Technology-enhanced learning (TEL), MuSA (Musical Saliency Analyzer), Saliency analysis, Music performance analysis, Musical expression, Musical talent development, Talent-Development-in-Achievement-Domains (TAD) Music Model, Self-directed learning (SDL), Self-regulated learning (SRL), Cognitive load, Non-real-time feedback, Master-apprentice model, Constructivism, Scaffolding, Aural modeling, Visual modeling, Metacognition

Chapter 1

Introduction

Chances are, if you're reading this thesis, you've either learned or are currently learning to play a musical instrument. For those who are musically adept—congratulations! You've likely benefited from a fortunate combination of musical aptitude, sufficient financial resources, and a supportive environment. You've also probably spent countless hours on **deliberate practice**, which generally comprises a set of activities designed by an external source, often a teacher, for performance improvement and musical talent development [2].

In this thesis, **musical talent** refers to the demonstration of competence after accounting for an individual's training, genetics, and environment [3, 4, 5]. Though practice alone doesn't guarantee musical talent, it remains a cornerstone of skill development [6, 7]. Despite this, many aspiring musicians struggle to practice effectively without consistent, high-quality feedback and instead develop ineffective practice strategies [8, 9]. This challenge stems in part from the enduring dominance of the **master-apprentice model** in music education, a tradition that emphasizes in-person instruction from a skilled mentor [10, 11]. While valuable, this model is often inaccessible to those without ample time, money, or proximity to expert teachers. Additionally, challenges in effective independent practice, whether or not a teacher is involved, also arise from the neglect of reflection during the cycle of self-regulated deliberate practice [9, 12, 13].

To help bridge this gap, there is a growing interest in **technology-enhanced learning (TEL)**—an educational approach that integrates technology to make practice and learning more accessible, engaging, and effective. TEL emphasizes constructivist learning principles [14, 15], in which students actively build their own understanding rather than passively absorb information. If implemented correctly, it can prioritize learner independence [16] and specialized feedback [17, 18, 19], which is important for closing the gap between a learner’s current skills and their goals [20]. However, many TEL tools used in music education are **(1)** too focused on beginners, **(2)** do not allow flexible interpretation of personalized feedback, **(3)** still may require an expert to derive meaning from existing non-real-time tools that can be used for performance analysis, and **(4)** focus mostly on the practice/performance part of learning rather than reflection. This thesis argues that **MuSA (Musical Salience Analyzer)** can address such gaps by algorithmically highlighting salient moments based on the variability of specific musical aspects, thereby narrowing the focus of performance reflection. Measuring variability in low-level audio features has been shown to effectively indicate musically important moments across a variety of instruments and contexts [21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26]. MuSA leverages this principle to provide feedback on potentially significant musical moments in a manner partially analogous to self-reflection stimulated by a teacher, thereby contributing to the broader development of TEL for music.

1.1 Motivation

While TEL has found successful applications in music education, its use has largely remained peripheral. Most music educators employ technology for secondary tasks such as preparing handouts, creating musical scores or presentations, showing videos, or recording classroom activities [27, 28, 29, 30, 31]. In doing so, the constructivist potential of TEL is often sidelined, and the traditional teacher-centered model once again becomes dominant as students still depend on instructors during the learning process. This is particularly important because most music practice occurs independently, regardless of whether or not a teacher is involved in the learning process

[32, 33]. Therefore, effective TEL tools must not only complement the master-apprentice model but also be capable of guiding learners during solitary practice sessions, both in active performance and reflection.

Despite ongoing efforts by researchers, teachers, and engineers to develop TEL platforms that circumvent traditional music instruction models, progress in this area remains limited and uneven. For instance, most existing and accessible TEL music platforms are typically geared toward beginners [34], with popular tools like YouSician¹ (primarily for guitarists) and SkyNote² (an experimental tool for violinists) offering real-time score tracking and visual feedback to help students develop basic technical skills such as pitch accuracy and rhythmic timing. While the aforementioned tools play an important role in early music education, they leave several key gaps unaddressed:

1. **Cognitive Overload from Real-Time Feedback:** Feedback is a well-established element of the learning process [35], and frequent input is critical for refining performance strategies [36]. However, while feedback can be delivered either during (**real-time**) or after a performance (**non-real-time**), real-time feedback may impose a **cognitive load**, or learning effort [37, 38], that ultimately hinders rather than supports practice [39, 40].
2. **Neglect of Musical Expression in TEL Tools:** In music pedagogy, from beginner to advanced levels, the primary focus remains on enforcing technical correctness [41, 42]. Thus, many TEL platforms emphasize technical accuracy (e.g., pitch, tempo), often reducing feedback to binary judgments of “correct” or “incorrect” based on fixed standards such as sheet music. This focus overlooks the development of **musical expression**, or the ability to intentionally shape timing, dynamics, pitch, and timbre to convey emotional or stylistic intent [43], a skill that becomes increasingly more relevant as musicians advance [44, 45].
3. **Limited Use of Self-Recording in TEL:** Video- and audio-recording are proven methods for goal setting, enhancing self-assessment [46, 47, 48, 49, 50],

¹<http://yousician.com/>

²<https://appskynote.com/>

and fostering musical expression [51, 52, 53], an area shown to benefit from technological integration [53, 54, 55]. However, most existing tools for evaluating recordings (e.g., Sonic Visualiser³, Audacity⁴, LARA⁵) are designed primarily for engineers or researchers and may require expert musicians with sound and music computing backgrounds to interpret complex feedback, such as relating tempograms or pitch curves to specific performance moments, undermining their integration into independent practice regimens.

4. **Lack of Saliency Analysis in Existing TEL Recording Tools:** While several TEL platforms allow non-real-time analysis of performance recordings, few explicitly incorporate **saliency analysis** to highlight expressive or pedagogically significant moments. Aforementioned tools like Sonic Analyser provide acoustic data and technical metrics, but do not identify the points of high musical variability or expressive intent that can guide learners toward more nuanced understanding of performance. This represents a critical gap in using recordings for actionable musical feedback.
5. **Neglect of Reflection During Practice:** Many platforms emphasize feedback during practice, leaving little time for reflection, a crucial component of self-regulated learning (SRL) [56, 57, 58, 59], which allows learners to identify challenges, address them, and evaluate progress [60]. Reflection is often neglected [9, 12, 13], and although using audio- and video-recordings can effectively support performance improvement [61], it is underutilized due to time constraints, limited knowledge of reflective strategies, and the perception that reflection is less productive than playing. Few tools, moreover, focus on streamlining the process of reviewing recordings to make reflection during practice more efficient.
6. **Lack of Focus on Accessibility and Shareability:** Adoption is often hindered by limited accessibility, as many tools prioritize desktop applications over more accessible web-based platforms. Since educators shape pedagogy and can serve as gatekeepers [62, 63], ensuring that new music technologies

³<https://www.sonicvisualiser.org/>

⁴<https://www.audacityteam.org/>

⁵<https://www.hslu.ch/en/lucerne-school-of-music/forschung/performance/lara/>

are easy to share and promote should become a central development priority.

Thus, there remains a significant gap in the development of accessible, non-real-time music performance analysis tools both for independent use and adoption in traditional learning settings that streamline reflection during practice. Because existing tools that can be used for non-real-time performance evaluation **(1)** may require interpretation from subject matter experts and **(2)** are not easily shareable due to a lack of web accessibility, it was important to frame the development MuSA, around these challenges.

Mentioned previously, one of the central concepts underlying MuSA’s facilitation of practice reflection is **salience analysis**, here defined as identifying key moments in a performance that are significant, either technically or expressively, for particular musical aspects. Although most music lessons focus on reading notation and technique [64, 65, 66, 41], teachers also use strategies to draw students’ attention to important passages or features. These strategies include exaggerating speech, gesture, and aural modeling [67] as well as explaining how aspects like articulation, dynamics, and tempo can be applied at specific moments to achieve desired effects [68]. Moreover, literature in music performance analysis (MPA) suggests that variability during key musical aspects like timbre, dynamics, tempo indicate moments of musical saliency [21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26]. MuSA aims to take advantage of these ideas about salient moments in music performance, identify variable moments algorithmically, and present such moments so that learners can receive performance-specific feedback even when practicing independently and narrow their scope of reflection.

1.2 Objectives

To develop MuSA, the following objectives guided the research and development process:

1. **Define a musical talent development framework** to establish the broader context for musical growth. This thesis adopts the **Talent-Development-in-Achievement-Domains (TAD) Music Model** [44, 45] to describe stages

of musical talent development and how students progress through them. Understanding these stages allows for a theoretical evaluation of how MuSA can support learners as they develop musical talent.

2. **Compile a background of common practice strategies and learning frameworks** used in both independent and traditional master-apprentice settings. Doing so informs how MuSA can be designed to integrate smoothly into existing practice routines and facilitate performance reflection.
3. **Emphasize musical expression as a core dimension of musical talent** to guide MuSA's development toward providing flexible, personalized feedback (fostering expressive skills) rather than solely binary "correct"/"incorrect" judgments (training technical skills).
4. **Evaluate existing TEL platforms for music practice and performance analysis**, focusing on their capacity for personalized feedback and support for learning musical expression. This includes reviewing online learning strategies and assessing both real-time and non-real-time feedback applications (especially performance analysis tools) to identify gaps in TEL music platforms.

To evaluate the pedagogical value of MuSA, a mixed-methods study was conducted. The study examined whether detecting salient moments and providing visual feedback affected musicians' self-rated and objective performance (i.e., reflection) on features like pitch, dynamics, and tempo. The key contributions of this thesis include:

1. **The design and implementation of MuSA**, a TEL platform that analyzes salient moments of a music performance based on different musical aspects and can be used outside the traditional master-apprentice model to facilitate performance reflection.
2. **Empirical findings from a mixed-methods user study** that may inform future integrations of performance analysis technologies into independent music learning, specifically with regards to self-awareness during music performance.
3. **A direction for future explorations** that can further develop the MuSA

web application and explore how presenting salient moments to learners may not only support performance correction relative to a reference audio but also enhance musical understanding and reflection during practice through the visualization of performance recordings.

The thesis is structured as follows: Chapter 1 introduces the research context and motivation; Chapter 2 reviews relevant literature and the state of the art; Chapter 3 details the design and development of MuSA; Chapter 4 outlines the evaluation study done on MuSA; and Chapter 5 discusses implications and future work.

1.3 Code Accessibility

All code is accessible through Github⁶. Both MuSA⁷ and the MuSA evaluation study⁸ can be accessed online.

⁶<https://github.com/isabelleoktay/audio-analyzer/>

⁷<https://analyzer.appskynote.com/>

⁸<https://analyzer.appskynote.com/testing/>

Chapter 2

Background

2.1 Foundations of Musical Talent Development

Musical talent is often perceived as innate, yet it more accurately emerges from the interaction between individual predispositions and cultivated skills [3]. Recognizing this interplay is essential for explaining why some musicians excel and for identifying how technology-enhanced learning (TEL) can best support their development. This perspective not only justifies the creation of MuSA but also clarifies the pedagogical principles that shape its core functionality.

Some elements of musical talent are less easily influenced. **Intelligence**, for example, is largely determined by genetics [69] and comprises a range of cognitive abilities such as perceptual speed [70] and reasoning ability [71]. Individuals also differ in their auditory sensory discrimination even before receiving formal musical education, a capability known as **musical aptitude** [3]. **Environmental factors** can also predispose talent, as children whose abilities are recognized early by parents are more likely to receive enriched musical opportunities [72]. Other aspects are more directly shaped through intentional effort. **Practice**, for instance, is widely regarded as a pillar of talent development, as no one is born knowing how to read sheet music, play scales, or sight-sing. Early engagement with music further develops technical skills and fosters personality traits such as willpower and motivation, creating a

foundation for the continual accrual of musical knowledge [73, 74].

However, the relative impacts of these factors on developing musical talent remain debated, with practice being a focal point of contention. In this discussion, the term practice refers specifically to **deliberate practice**, which is understood as a set of activities typically designed by an external source, often a teacher, with the explicit goal of improving performance [6, 2, 7, 75]. This definition provides a narrower, more operational measure of practice, aligning with much of the literature against which competing influences (e.g., intelligence, musical aptitude) have been evaluated [4, 5].

Research shows that accumulated practice hours are the strongest predictor of technical skills like sight-reading [6, 7]. Yet meta-analyses estimate practice explains only 23% to 37% of the variance in overall music achievement [4, 5]. Critics of these findings cite methodological issues, including inconsistent definitions of deliberate practice [76]. Even so, genetic factors such as intelligence may surpass practice in predicting musical development—especially in beginners—and may predict sight-reading performance after controlling for practice [77, 78, 7]. Environmental influences also interact with genetic ones, as musically inclined parents may both foster enriched environments and pass on traits predisposing children to formal training. Such inherited tendencies to select and shape environments, known as **gene–environment transactions** [69], suggest that musical experiences may themselves be partly heritable.

2.1.1 The TAD Music Model

While practice is vital for developing instrumental technique and personal skills, it operates alongside—and in constant interaction with—genetic, cognitive, and environmental influences. To situate these factors within a coherent developmental trajectory, this thesis adopts the **Talent-Development-in-Achievement-Domains (TAD) Music Model** [44, 45]. This empirically validated framework outlines distinct stages of talent acquisition and identifies psychological **predictors** that track progression over time, integrating both predispositions and learned skills. Using

this model allows MuSA’s design to be tailored toward a clearly defined audience of learners.

The TAD Music Model is not the first attempt to conceptualize musical talent development, but it is distinctive in its use of measurable predictors to link time and achievement [79]. Earlier models overemphasized genetic and environmental factors [80, 81, 82, 83], which are challenging to evaluate empirically due to the cost, complexity, and scarcity of longitudinal studies [84, 42, 85]. As a result, purely genetic- or environment-based models have proven less reliable for predicting long-term musical achievement.

Figure 1: The Talent-Development-in-Achievement-Domains Framework [44]

The TAD Music Model (Figure 1) identifies four stages of musical talent development, each with characteristic predictors and learning needs:

1. **Aptitude:** innate mental and physical abilities, such as melodic, rhythmic, and tonal sensitivity, that predict a natural capacity for musical success [86].
2. **Competence:** the acquisition of skills needed for independent practice, expressive improvement, and repertoire expansion. Key predictors include a

growth mindset [87, 88], self-motivation [79, 89], musical self-concept [89, 88], motor skills [90], and deliberate practice.

3. **Expertise:** a level of achievement characterized by peer recognition, creative problem-solving, and public engagement [91]. Predictors include psychological stability, openness, conscientiousness, resilience, and focused dedication [79].
4. **Transformational achievement:** a level of expertise marked by significant, influential, and creative contributions. This stage is less predictable, shaped by factors such as chance, opportunity, creative potential [92], musical form [93, 94], and strategies for sustaining high-level output [95].

The TAD Music Model shows that musicians at different stages need different kinds of support. For example, in the *Aptitude* stage, a player needs basic technical training to turn natural ability into core **technical skills**. These include sight-reading, posture, ear-training, and the ability to play a piece with regards to musical aspects like timing, intensity, pitch, and timbre. On the other hand, in the *Competence* stage, the focus shifts to strengthening technique while also developing a personal style and expressive voice. **Musical expression** involves shaping musical aspects to convey a work's emotional character and connect a performer's interpretation with a listener's experience [43, 96].

As Section 2.5 demonstrates, many TEL music tools focus on technical skills, providing binary feedback (correct/incorrect) tied to the musical score. This approach misses the interpretive dialogue essential to modern teaching frameworks and leaves a gap for musicians who need to develop their expressive abilities. Moreover, such tools are necessary to guide the reflective aspect of practice, which is guided by the learner's interpretation of their performance after actively practicing. Therefore, in addition to technical skills, we develop MuSA in such a way as to facilitate musical expression in parallel, as both are essential for developing musical talent and are a core focus of TEL in music education.

2.2 Practice Strategies in Music Education

Building on the factors shaping musical talent discussed in Section 2.1, this thesis focuses on practice, since it is the factor that learners can control most. To design TEL practice tools effectively, it is important to understand the different types of practice that influence talent development. Ericsson (2016) identified three types [97]:

1. **Naive practice:** Playing an instrument for enjoyment without specific goals or structured improvement.
2. **Purposeful practice:** Goal-oriented practice done independently, without continuous expert guidance or structured feedback.
3. **Deliberate practice:** Highly structured practice guided by a teacher with deep expertise.

The difference in performance outcomes between purposeful and deliberate practice is substantial. In Ericsson (1993) seminal study of violinists at the Music Academy in West Berlin, the most accomplished musicians had accumulated the highest number of deliberate practice hours [6]. Later meta-analyses suggested that deliberate practice accounted for only 23% [4] to 37% [5] of performance variation. Ericsson et al. (2019) argued that these studies used incorrect definitions, and when deliberate practice is properly defined, its explanatory power rises to 61% [76], indicating a strong influence in musical talent development. TEL tools like MuSA support deliberate practice by strengthening the development of musical talent while making learning more effective and accessible through cognitive and pedagogical strategies.

2.2.1 The Master-Apprentice Model

Given the central role of deliberate practice, it is unsurprising that traditional music education has long relied on the **master–apprentice** model, one popular learning strategy. In this approach, students receive in-person guidance from an experienced tutor, and the musical score serves as the core of instruction [98, 99, 100, 101, 10, 11]. Despite the rise of independent learning and online resources, this model

remains dominant in conservatories and higher education worldwide [102], across both Western and non-Western traditions [103].

Most learners do not have constant access to detailed feedback available through conservatories and master-apprenticeship that can enable reflection, receiving only a single weekly lesson [104]. Left to practice alone for most of their time, these learners may develop incorrect techniques, lose direction, or form ineffective habits. Without consistent guidance, even motivated students can reduce deliberate practice to purposeful, or even naive, practice [105, 9, 8, 76].

To address this challenge, experts have developed teaching approaches that focus on the learner and their needs rather than just the tutor or musical score. The following sections examine constructivist strategies such as dialogic teaching, scaffolding, and modeling, which can promote learner autonomy, develop skills for more effective independent practice, and facilitate reflection. These frameworks guided MuSA's design, providing a basis to support and enhance practice when expert guidance is limited.

2.2.2 Constructivism and Dialogic Teaching

Constructivist learning principles position the learner as an active participant rather than a passive recipient of instruction. In **constructivist theory**, the teacher acts as a facilitator, designing activities that help learners build understanding by reorganizing and integrating prior knowledge [14, 106, 107, 15, 108]. This **learner-centered teaching (LCT)**, in contrast to the master-apprentice model's emphasis on teacher and score authority, can provide the benefits of expert feedback while also fostering a collaborative environment that gives a student ownership over their learning [109]. Components of LCT include the use of interactive, personalized learning activities and the inclusion of technology to manage learning outside of the classroom. LCT has shown to lead to higher learning outcomes and motivation across a variety of fields including medicine [110], mathematics [111], and music [112, 113].

A practical expression of LCT in music education is **dialogic teaching**, an approach in which sustained dialogue between teacher and student becomes the primary medium for learning. In dialogic teaching, rather than delivering one-way instructions, teachers engage learners through questioning, reflection, and collaborative exploration, enabling real-time adaptation of guidance to meet evolving needs [114, 115]. This open feedback channel encourages students to co-construct their own interpretations, which is why MuSA’s performance feedback avoids binary correct/incorrect labeling: MuSA is designed as a learner-centered tool for reflection rather than a score-centered tool for correction.

2.2.3 Scaffolding

Another LCT approach is **scaffolding**, which involves tailoring support to a learner’s current ability and gradually transferring responsibility for performance and interpretation to the student. This process is rooted in the work of Vygotsky, a core contributor to constructivism. It leverages his concept of the **zone of proximal development**, which is the range of tasks a learner can perform with assistance but not independently, and provides tailored support that gradually decreases as the learner’s competence grows [106, 116]. The key principles of scaffolding (Figure 2) are:

1. **Contingency:** The teacher’s support must be continually adapted to the learner’s current skill level, preventing the learner from being overwhelmed or unchallenged [117, 118, 119].
2. **Fading:** Support is gradually decreased as the learner’s competence grows. For example, a teacher may initially provide extensive modeling but reduce assistance as the learner becomes more proficient with a skill or piece [120, 118].
3. **Transfer of Responsibility:** The goal of scaffolding is to shift learning responsibility to the learner, fostering autonomous competence so they can perform tasks independently [121].
4. **Cyclical Process:** Scaffolding is a recurring cycle. Once a learner masters one sub-goal (e.g., a basic bow hold on a violin), the teacher introduces a new,

slightly more challenging sub-goal. The scaffolding process then begins again for this new task [122].

Figure 2: Conceptual model of scaffolding [118].

MuSA can be contextualized within the scaffolding framework by providing a form of *contingency* and facilitating the *transfer of responsibility* by acting as an SRL tool. While scaffolding typically relies on a dedicated teacher to tailor support, MuSA's feedback can act as an TEL intermediary. For example, if a learner is focused on a specific performance outcome, they can analyze a performance recording with MuSA. The platform then responds by highlighting interesting salient moments (see Section 2.3.3) during different musical aspects. This reflects how a teacher provides *contingency* by indicating salient moments in a student's performance that may not be obvious to them. The goal is to initiate a *transfer of responsibility* for that specific task by helping the learner understand what to listen for, what performance outcomes to strive for, and what tools exist to help them practice.

2.2.4 Self-Regulated Learning

Self-regulated learning (SRL) emerges through the *transfer of responsibility* in scaffolding [122]. A self-regulated learner can identify challenges, address them, and evaluate progress toward a task [60]. For example, when learning scales, such a learner plans fingerings, monitors accuracy, and draws on available tools to guide practice independently of the teacher.

SRL models. Zimmerman (1989, 2000) introduced a tri-phase SRL model comprising **1)** forethought (planning), **2)** performance, and **3)** self-reflection [56, 57]. Later refinements, such as Zimmerman & Moylan (2009), expanded these phases into subprocesses relevant to skill-based learning [58]. In music education, Hatfield, Halvari, and Lemyre (2016) applied this framework and confirmed that planning, practice, and reflection represent key components for optimizing instrumental learning and sustaining self-regulation (Figure 3) [59].

Planning, practice, and reflection in SRL. In the *forethought*, students set goals and structure their sessions by selecting objectives (e.g., mastering a passage, improving intonation, or developing phrasing), strategies (slow practice, rhythmic variation, hands/voices separately), and time allocations. Planning prevents aimless repetition and aligns effort with long-term learning. The *performance* phase involves deliberate engagement with the instrument—focused repetition, experimentation, application of technical exercises, and ongoing micro-adjustments based on auditory and kinesthetic feedback. In the *self-reflection* phase, students consolidate learning by reviewing progress and strategies. Reflection transforms repetition into learning by revealing error patterns, guiding subsequent planning, and cultivating autonomy, self-monitoring, and motivation.

Neglect of reflection in SRL. Despite its importance, reflection is often neglected [12]. Both children [9] and advanced musicians [13] tend to focus more on “doing” than on evaluating their work, though Hallam (2001) notes that successful expert musicians employ reflection via SRL to assess their own performance, to rec-

Figure 3: Three-phase model of SRL in music education, adapted from Hatfield, Halvari, and Lemyre (2016) [59]

ognize positive aspects and also critical points for improvement, and to select, apply and monitor learning strategies during musical practice [123]. However, barriers to all musicians for including reflection and cultivating successful reflection skills include time pressure, limited knowledge of reflective strategies, and the perception that reflection is less productive than playing. As a result, practice can become mechanical and disconnected from long-term progress. This is one of the reasons why MuSA was developed: to ideally better facilitate practice reflection.

2.2.5 Self-Directed Learning

SRL and LCT must also be understood within the growing body of independent learners. While employing LCT and SRL strategies typically involve a teacher, the number of completely independent learners is rising due to the increased availability of online resources and financial constraints. Since a significant amount of

learning occurs during independent practice, even for students with a teacher, the **self-directed learning (SDL)** framework can help learners structure their own learning potentially using TEL platforms, like MuSA, as a supplement for teacher feedback.

SRL versus SDL. As defined in Section 2.2.3, SRL is an learning outcome during scaffolding that allows a learner identify problems, define practice solutions, and track progress for individual tasks. SDL, in contrast, is a metacognitive approach that employs SRL on a macro-level to prioritize broader skills [124]. Learners who employ SDL “moderate, control, and evaluate their learning” independently [125, 126] by following three key dimensions. The first, *self-management*, highlights actions such as controlling tasks, resources, and goal-setting. The second, *self-monitoring*, is the reflective part of the learning process, helping learners refine the strategies they’ve employed. Lastly, *motivation* initiates and sustains a learner’s engagement with a task [125, 126].

Gibbons et al. found that employing SDL principles is particularly helpful for guiding adolescent and adult learners [127], a population that often has limited access to LCT tutorship. Effective SDL in music education also correlates positively with technology use, at least among music students at the university level, because the use of technology can supplement personalized feedback and guidance when a teacher is unavailable [128]. For example, a mostly independent learner studying woodwind or string instruments might use a tool like Tonestro¹ to as a lessons library (*self-management*), and online forum like Reddit’s r/LearnMusic² to receive feedback on their learning methods and resources (*self-monitoring*), and forScore³ as a progress tracker (*motivation*). SDL highlights the importance of both using existing technology to facilitate independent learning and developing new TEL platforms, like MuSA, to address its unmet needs. For an overview of TEL tools and the gap that MuSA fills, see Section 2.5.

¹<https://www.tonestro.com/>

²<https://www.reddit.com/r/Learnmusic/>

³<https://forscore.co/>

2.3 Feedback

Whether a learner has access to a teacher or not, **feedback** is the basis of learning and self-reflection. It remains the primary mechanism for closing the gap between current ability and intended performance [35, 129]. In other words, feedback helps a learner understand how to modify their behavior to achieve a specific performance goal.

Learner Stage	Feedback Level	Feeding Up: <i>Where am I going?</i>	Feeding Back: <i>How am I going?</i>	Feeding Forward: <i>What do I have to do next?</i>
NOVICE	TASK	Feeding Up Prompts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For this piece[*] we will learn . . . Performing successfully will look like (provide model) The key criteria for success are . . . We are trying to do the following . . . 	Feedback Prompts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> You have/haven't met the performance goal because . . . You have/haven't met the success criteria because . . . Your work does/doesn't yet sound the way we want because . . . 	Feed Forward Prompts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To fully meet the challenges of mastering this piece, you could . . . Adding/removing _____ would improve your performance by . . . Addressing the following performance issues would improve your playing . . .
		Feedback Strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce complexity (e.g. reduce tempo, length of excerpt, range) Provide recordings or live models of target performance Identify misunderstandings Diagnose student's current performance level in order to understand how to make tasks responsive to learner's needs and to set incremental performance goals 	Feedback Strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Avoid over-emphasis on analyzing errors Provide immediate feedback Match feedback to success criteria set for the 'ideal' performance 	Feed Forward Strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use language from the success criteria to direct the learner toward appropriate musical and technical goals Use scaffolding to support the learner Feed forward must be timely (i.e., not given when it is no longer of use to the learner) Set appropriate challenges Refer to and remind learner of the performance goals
PROFICIENT	PROCESS	Feeding Up Prompts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The key musical/technical challenges of this piece are . . . The strategies you use here are the same for . . . Skills you will need to apply to master this music include . . . Questions you could ask about this piece include . . . Strategies you will need to identify in order to practice this music include . . . 	Feedback Prompts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Your understanding of the key ideas/concepts of this piece is . . . Your thinking about how to interpret this piece is . . . You demonstrated _____ performance skills to a _____ level. You used _____ practice strategies to a _____ level. 	Feed Forward Prompts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> You could improve your performance of this section by . . . Thinking further about _____ could improve your performance by . . . Practicing _____ would further improve your performance. You could improve your practice skills by . . .
		Feeding Up Strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use graphical organizers to help learner understand the learning process Vary scaffolding techniques Increase complexity of performance tasks Reduce scaffolding to encourage learner independence Set mastery goals for performance mastery 	Feedback Strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amount of feedback can be increased Feedback complexity can increase Use prompts or cues to help the learner assess themselves 	Feed Forward Strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increasing amount of feed forward as the learner becomes more proficient Complexity of feed forward can increase as the learner becomes more capable Use prompts or cues to help the learner assess themselves Clarify/set challenges to identify what the next level of performance could be
ADVANCED	SELF-REGULATORY	Feeding Up Prompts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How will you use the learning intention to improve your performance? How can you use the success criteria to help you practice this piece? How can you monitor your progress in learning this piece? 	Feedback Prompts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are you on track with this piece to meet your performance goals? How do you know you aren't on track? To what degree are you satisfying the success criteria? Are you on track to achieve your performance goal? How do you know? 	Feed Forward Prompts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How could you deepen your mastery/interpretation of this piece? How could you further improve your performance? If you were to start to learn this again, what strategies would you use to improve your learning? What is the next step for your learning? How do you know that's the next step?
		Feeding Up Strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce emphasis on exemplars Set mastery and performance goals with the learner 	Feedback Strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delay feedback Learners may only require verification feedback for their own evaluations 	Feed Forward Strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delay feedback Reduce reliance on teacher for feedback Encourage autonomy and self-regulated learning behaviors

* For each of these, 'piece' could be replaced by exercise, task, excerpt or other musically related challenge

Figure 4: A matrix indicating how feedback dimensions and cognitive levels interact to inform different feedback strategies [130].

Hattie et al. (2007) describe three complementary feedback dimensions: *feed up* (clarifying the goal), *feed back* (evaluating current performance), and *feed forward* (guiding next steps). Together, these dimensions link past, present, and future learning [20]. Their effectiveness depends on aligning with the learner's cognitive level: *task-focused* (accuracy of notes, rhythm, or dynamics), *process-focused* (practice strategies and error detection), or *self-regulatory* (goal-setting and independent monitoring) [131, 130]. When misaligned, feedback risks being misunderstood or ignored [131].

McPherson et al.'s (2022) feedback matrix (see Figure 4) shows how different feedback dimensions and cognitive levels interact to determine the type of feedback

needed at various stages of learning a musical piece [130]. For example, in the context of *feeding back*, a novice learner with a new piece might benefit from task-level feedback that provides binary, correct/incorrect feedback on technical skills like intonation, dynamics, and tempo. In contrast, a proficient or advanced learner might benefit more from a tool that also engages the process-level by helping them refine past performances to interpret the same piece on their own, which also engages self-reflection.

2.3.1 Cognitive Load

As implied by McPherson et al.'s (2022) feedback matrix, input frequency is an important feedback element for skill improvement [36]. Feedback frequency be delivered as either **real-time** (during a task) or **non-real-time/postsession** (after a task). Frequency can impact **cognitive load**, or the mental effort required for learning, which in turn affects how a learner receives and processes that feedback. Cognitive load may also be interpreted as one of the reasons music learners struggle to consistently reflect on their progress in the three-stage cycle of SRL [132].

Intrinsic, Extraneous, and Germane. There are three distinct kinds of cognitive load. *Intrinsic load* is the effort required to learn material. For example, the simultaneous demands of a following complex score and communicating expression may result in a high intrinsic load compared to completing these tasks individually. *Extraneous load* describes any unnecessary mental effort caused by a poor instructional design or guidance. Lastly, *germane load* is the effort that goes directly into learning, building knowledge, and storing knowledge into long-term memory [37, 38].

Real-Time Versus Non-Real-Time. Real-time feedback may increase intrinsic cognitive load for a variety of tasks across different domains. Lurie et al. (2009) argue that high-frequency real-time feedback contributes to decline in performance during tasks with high *demand-variance*, or those completed in noisy information environments with unpredictable performance conditions [40]. Similarly, Rego et al. (2023) found that postsession feedback improved physician performance and reduced

cognitive load when receiving feedback on physician-patient interactions [39].

Cognitive load of real-time feedback in music. In music, learning a new piece has high demand-variance because learners must focus on individual notes while also considering broader musical phrases and expressive goals. Real-time feedback is a form of very high-frequency feedback that may induce tunnel vision, causing learners to fixate on single note corrections while losing sight of a larger musical phrase or expressive intent. Music-specific studies measuring cognitive load with technology-assisted real-time feedback show that both haptic [133, 119] and visual [134, 135] real-time feedback may increase cognitive load. Çorlu, K. M., et al. (2015) found that adding a secondary cognitive task while musicians performed a piece reduced their expressive abilities [136], and Blanco et al. (2021) demonstrated that even when real-time visual feedback improved bowing movements, the sound quality of a performance decreased [134].

Potential drawbacks of non-real-time feedback in music. While real-time feedback has been shown to increase cognitive load, a key issue with non-real-time feedback is the potential for miscommunication. Even when tutors successfully identify moments for correction, students may fail to interpret the teacher's instructions [137]. For example, at the end of an exercise, a teacher might give feedback on a learner's dynamic control or posture, but the student may not be able to identify where in the performance that feedback is most applicable. However, including audio and video recordings of performances during non-real-time feedback can better "close the [feedback] gap" [129] by allowing teachers to identify key moments for improvement. Audio and video recordings are already a strategy employed by teachers and students alike for the reflection phase of SRL [138, 61]. However, reviewing these recordings may also create additional cognitive load, as learners may be unsure which parts to focus on for reflection. This can increase *extraneous* load, since mental effort is spent on tasks that are not optimally organized for learning (e.g., deciding which parts of a recording to focus on during self-reflection) [38].

2.3.2 Modeling

One popular method for generating feedback in music education and potentially reducing cognitive load when learning a new task is **modeling**, in which a teacher demonstrates a desired sound or technique often based on a learner's current performance state [139]. Modeling can take two forms: **aural modeling**, where learners listen to and emulate expert performances to build internal musical representations [51, 140, 141, 142], and **visual modeling**, which emphasizes physical aspects like posture and fingering with heavy reliance on written notation [143].

Aural versus visual modeling. While both visual and aural modeling have value, research shows that aural modeling has higher learning outcomes for both technical skills and musical expression since aural modeling focuses on external outcomes (how the instrument sounds) rather than just the internal action (how the body performs) [144, 145, 68, 146, 147, 148, 113]. This conclusion aligns with Meissner's (2021) dialogic teaching framework, which combines cognitive load theory, dialogic teaching, and modeling-based feedback, suggesting that focusing on the overall outcome rather than becoming entangled in minutia can manage cognitive load [149]. Additionally, over-reliance on visual modeling may weaken a student's ability to connect their physical actions with the resulting sound [150]. As a result, musicians may struggle to develop **musical understanding**, or the ability to recognize and manipulate patterns and relationships in music [151]. When modeling emphasizes symbolic information, it becomes score-centered rather than learner-centered, focusing on *what* to do instead of *how* and *why*, thus failing to work towards musical understanding. This is one reason MuSA relies on the sound of an individual's performance instead of the sheet music behind it.

Multi-Modal Modeling. Modeling is often paired with other learning methods in a combination known as **multi-modal modeling** to further enhance learning outcomes. For instance, while modeling alone can foster dependence, combining it with strategies like verbal feedback encourages students' interpretive thinking and internal musical representations [149]. This is because verbal teaching methods,

such as using metaphors or explicit explanations, are shown to improve musical understanding and strengthen expressive performance [152], which is in line with LCT dialogic teaching outcomes [112, 113].

2.3.3 Salient Moments

Often, when providing feedback using modeling, teachers naturally highlight important performance moments by exaggerating musical aspects like intonation, dynamics, or timing during model performances [67]. This thesis defines these highlighted moments as **salient moments**. A teacher may indicate salient moments as areas during a performance for technical correction or those where a learner can employ their own musical interpretation relative to an existing norm (like written notation). These may include pitch errors, timing issues, or expressive changes that deserve closer attention. Especially when focusing on musical expression, identifying a salient moment does not inherently imply assigning positive or negative value to it; rather, the identification of a salient moment can start conversation about expressive intent (dialogic teaching) or clarify if a learner's technique or choices are actually leading to their intended expressive outcome.

2.3.4 Synthesizing SRL, SDL, Feedback, and MuSA

Looking at the TAD Model, deliberate practice, scaffolding, and SRL, one theme stands out: reflection is essential at all stages of talent development for turning repetition into real progress, yet it is often neglected. Learners may plan and practice carefully, but without structured opportunities to evaluate their performance, practice can become mechanical and disconnected from long-term goals [153]. As Section 2.5.2 discusses, many music learners use self-recording to reflect on their playing, but this method is often inefficient: reviewing full sessions takes time [154], adds cognitive load, and can lead to passive listening that misses subtle mistakes [138]. As a result, reflection tends to be occasional rather than systematic. MuSA addresses this problem by automatically highlighting salient moments and focusing reflection tasks. By reducing the time and effort needed for review, a tool like MuSA

can make reflection easier to do regularly. This approach helps integrate reflection into the practice cycle, improves planning through feedback on recurring patterns (e.g., “intonation drifts sharp in high positions”), and supports independent learning while hopefully developing critical listening and self-assessment skills.

2.4 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge

Designing a new TEL tool to support the reflection process in music practice, such as MuSA, requires guidance beyond broad psychological or cognitive principles. Models such as **Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK)** and its expansion through **Technology Mapping (TM)** provide a structured way to connect these principles to the specific challenges of music education. The following section outlines how this model, which emphasizes the interplay of technology, pedagogy, content, and the affective domain, informs and justifies MuSA’s design.

TPCK. Around 20 years ago, researchers introduced Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK) to guide the design of TEL tools by emphasizing how subject knowledge, pedagogy, and technology intersect in teaching [155, 17, 18]. Angeli and Valanides (2013) expanded this framework with an instructional design approach called Technology Mapping, which specifies how tools should be developed to use technology’s unique affordances for learning [19]. The principles of TPCK include:

1. **Find high-impact content:** Identify topics that are difficult for students to understand or for teachers to explain without the aid of technology.
2. **Create unique representations:** Develop new ways to present content that are only possible with technology, making it easier to grasp.
3. **Leverage novel teaching methods:** Identify and use teaching strategies that are difficult or impossible to implement with traditional methods alone.
4. **Choose the right tools:** Select technology with the appropriate features to support the teaching and learning goals.
5. **Design learner-centered activities:** Create learner-centered classroom ac-

tivities that effectively integrate technology.

TM and the Affective Domain. Macrides and Angeli (2018) expanded Technology Mapping for music education by adding the affective domain (Figure 5) [156, 157]. This addition highlights that emotion, motivation, and personal expression are central to music learning, addressing a gap in the original framework [158], which only focused on pedagogical and cognitive aspects. Research shows that many students struggle with composition, improvisation, and listening because of limited skills or confidence [159, 160, 161]. By integrating the affective domain, the expanded model reframes these challenges as opportunities to connect technical learning with expression and emotion. Educators argue that musical experiences cannot be separated from their expressive character [162], and that emphasizing self-expression increases engagement and motivation [8, 151].

Using TPCK to Inform MuSA. MuSA’s design reflects this expanded model, which stresses that music learning involves both cognitive and emotional aspects [163]. MuSA provides flexible, non-corrective feedback that students can interpret in ways that suit their needs, echoing the view that focusing on expression can boost engagement [8]. By highlighting salient sections of a recording, MuSA directs attention to meaningful changes in dynamics, tempo, or articulation, features known to influence emotional responses [158, 164]. This approach lowers barriers for learners with different skill levels, since the focus is on recorded analysis rather than live performance [27]. At the same time, its saliency analysis supports SRL by helping students reflect on their playing and take more control of their progress, in line with TM’s emphasis on interactive, learner-centered use of technology [19, 163].

2.5 TEL Feedback Systems in Music Education

A wide range of TEL tools can support music learning, with different tools addressing different TPCK principles depending on their purpose, audience, and market focus. While the master–apprentice model still dominates music education [10, 11], technology is increasingly used both inside and outside the classroom by traditional

Figure 5: A Technology Mapping model showing the interrelations of musical elements and concepts, technology, and affect [156].

and independent learners. These tools range from basic devices like metronomes and tuners to advanced systems that provide personalized feedback on performance [138]. This section examines the current state of TEL for music performance and practice to show how MuSA addresses a gap in this area.

2.5.1 Online Resources

Internet Availability. The availability of TEL in music education would not be possible without the internet, which has been a powerful tool in the dissemination of information, particularly in regions where digital access is widespread. Internet connectivity has expanded across households in the United States and Europe, making these regions particularly relevant for examining technology’s role in music learning. A 2023 Pew Research Center survey reports that 95% of U.S. adults use the internet, 90% own a smartphone, and 80% have high-speed internet at home [165]. Similarly, the European Commission reported in 2021 that 96% of Europeans have access to a mobile phone, and 82% of households have internet access [166]. These statistics highlight the infrastructural foundation for digital learning tools in these regions.

YouTube. A 2022 Pew Research Center survey found that YouTube⁴ was the most widely used online video platform among American teenagers (96%) and European young adults (84%). YouTube serves as a primary hub for informal beginner learning via instructional mock video lesson demonstrating technique, exercises, and repertoire [138]. Advanced learners also use YouTube to access information addressing technical, philosophical, and career challenges. While the platform’s strengths lie in its accessibility, low cost, and self-pacing through video controls [138], its major limitation is the lack of personalized performance feedback.

Music Education Websites. Music forums and music education websites like Dave Conservatoire⁵, Music Theory⁶, My Music Theory⁷, and SmartMusic⁸ may fill

⁴<https://youtube.com/>

⁵<https://daveconservatoire.org/>

⁶<https://musictheory.net/>

⁷<https://mymusictheory.com/>

⁸<https://smartmusic.com/>

YouTube's gap by generating conversation about technique and theory, but without personalized performance feedback, these platforms don't address critical aspects of music talent development like posture, sound quality, or musical expression [138]. Young adult learners also rarely interact with these platforms and seem to gravitate towards unidirectional content [167], indicating that the content levied may be too tedious to learn without a dedicated instructor or a platform that engages better with the *motivation* or *self-regulation* principles of SDL.

Online Learning. Personalized performance feedback can be delivered remotely via online learning, which includes synchronous, asynchronous, and hybrid formats. Online learning is suggested to be as effective as in-person instruction [168, 169] and may expand access to master-apprentice learning in domains like piano [170]. Critics of online learning mention that reliance on SRL and student motivation may impact student engagement [171, 172]. Regardless, this remains a key challenge for independent learning. Higher education institutions have adopted tools that replicate real-world musical workspaces such as LoLa⁹, JackTrip¹⁰, and UltraGrid¹¹ to reduce location-based learning restrictions and promote student independence.

Online Collaboration. Online collaboration is another way to give personalized performance feedback and cultivate motivation. Platforms like AudioMovers¹², Source-Connect¹³, Sessionwire¹⁴, SonoBus¹⁵, and VST Connect¹⁶ offer products with professional-grade audio streaming for remote collaboration [173]. These tools prioritize high-quality sound, low-latency capabilities, and digital audio workstation integration, enabling remote music creation that may train creative and expressive skills, a key aspect of TPCK for effective technology implementation in music education [163]. Real-time "jamming" tools like MusicianLink¹⁷ and Artsmesh¹⁸ can

⁹<https://lola.conts.it/>

¹⁰<https://jacktrip.com/>

¹¹<https://ultragrid.cz/>

¹²<https://audiomovers.com/>

¹³<https://source-elements.com/products/source-connect/>

¹⁴<https://sessionwire.com/>

¹⁵<https://sonobus.net/>

¹⁶<https://steinberg.net/vst-connect/>

¹⁷<https://musicianlink.com/>

¹⁸<https://artsmesh.com/>

also facilitate collaboration without reliance on in-person sessions. However, these high-fidelity tools face challenges like latency, data loss, and high barrier-to-entry.

2.5.2 Non-Real-Time Recording Feedback

Audio and Video Recording. Leveraging audio and video recordings is another way to receive personalized performance feedback and is proven to improve one's own playing [61]. Many teachers already encourage students to make video record performances to review movements or gestures that are difficult to notice in real-time due to the high cognitive load of simultaneously performing and self-evaluating [138]. Separating performance and review enables more objective assessment as recordings, whether audio or video, allow musicians to analyze specific musical elements, compare recordings with those of teachers or professionals, and study physical technique in detail [138]. Reviewing recordings is also a tool for SRL and SDL by facilitating better musical understanding and setting practice goals [174]. However, despite the benefits of reviewing audio and video recordings, many learners fail to regularly review their recordings due to the time consuming nature of the process [154]. Studies show that using audio and video recordings to provide computer-assisted visual feedback can help musicians improve dynamic control and awareness by giving clear feedback on their expressive range [175].

Computer-Assisted Audio Recording Feedback. Audio recordings can be abstracted through the visualization of important musical aspects like frequency spectrum, fundamental frequency (pitch), intensity, and resonance areas (formants) using free audio analysis software like Praat¹⁹, Sonic Visualiser²⁰, Audacity²¹, or LARA²² [176]. These tools also form the basis of purpose-designed visual feedback tools that display different audio analyses at different screen locations, sometimes aligned with reference audio to interpret results. For pitched audio, these include

¹⁹<https://fon.hum.uva.nl/praat/>

²⁰<https://sonicvisualiser.org/>

²¹<https://audacityteam.org/>

²²<https://hslu.ch/en/lucerne-school-of-music/forschung/performance/lara/>

tools like Sing and See²³, VocaVista²⁴, and Tartini²⁵, while for percussive audio, they may include audio analysis software plugins like BeatRoot or OnsetDS from Sonic Analyser [176]. However, many of these visual feedback tools have complicated interfaces with a high barrier to entry for the average learner, may require an expert with a sound and music computing background to interpret results, or are primarily oriented to real-time rather than non-real-time feedback.

Computer-Assisted Video Recording Feedback. Video recordings can also be abstracted via visual feedback tools. Older systems relied on markers placed to track motion or mark clear contrast between an object and its background, like EyeWeb²⁶, which analyzes expressive performance. Purdue University’s AIM project is developing an experimental tool called the Evaluator²⁷ to assist string musicians with individual practice by analyzing a musician’s sound and video, comparing it to a digitized score to detect deviations in relevant musical aspects (intonation, rhythm, dynamics), and even offer posture correction suggestions. However, non-real-time video recording performance analysis software specialized to musical performances has not yet been deeply explored. General open-source video analysis tools like Kinovea²⁸ are available for studying body mechanics and gestures. Onform²⁹ is another tool, though specialized to sports performance, that allows instructors to give targeted feedback on video recordings using voice-overs and on-screen markup tools.

2.5.3 Real-Time Feedback

Computer-Assisted Real-Time Audio Feedback. While available tools for computer-assisted audio recording feedback are either experimental tools or aimed at those with production, engineering, or sound and music computing backgrounds, many tools have been developed to provide learners real-time feedback based on performance audio. Some of these tools include those already mentioned such as

²³<https://singandsee.com/>

²⁴<https://vocevista.com/en/>

²⁵<https://cs.otago.ac.nz/graphics/Geoff/tartini/index.html>

²⁶https://casapaganini.unige.it/eyesweb_bp

²⁷<https://github.com/Purdue-Artificial-Intelligence-in-Music/Evaluator-code>

²⁸<https://kinovea.org/>

²⁹<https://onform.com/>

EyesWeb, Sing and See, VocaVista, and Tartini. General real-time feedback for ear training has been explored with EarMaster³⁰. Real-time audio feedback for string instrument performance has been particularly explored with experimental open-source platforms Intonia³¹, which helps string players visualize intonation. More recently the SkyNote³² web application was developed to track a string player's pitch in real-time and overlay their pitch curve with a score, allowing learners to see if their pitch and timing correctly align with given notation. Plectrus [177, 178] is another experimental application developed for training intonation in novice string players. Other commercial platforms leveraging real-time audio feedback include Yousician³³, MakeMusic³⁴, Uberchord³⁵, and Tonestro³⁶, and Riyaz³⁷ which all compare user's real-time audio to a selected score. Cortosia³⁸ by KORG provides real-time feedback on features such as dynamics, pitch stability, timbre, and attack clarity, though receiving simultaneous aspects can make it difficult to independently assess each one.

Computer-Assisted Real-Time Video Feedback. Real-time video feedback is well illustrated by the iMaestro project, which created an “augmented mirror” that uses visualization and sonification to analyze a string player's gestures live. TELMI is another project for string players, offering real-time visual feedback on posture, gesture, and bowing, along with score-aligned features such as dynamics, pitch, and timbre [179]. The Evaluator instead compares student performances to pre-recorded examples with correct form. However, real-time video feedback systems remain less developed than audio ones, largely due to the technical demands of motion capture and the current limits of commercial AI motion-tracking software.

³⁰<https://earmaster.com/>

³¹<https://intonia.com/index.shtml>

³²<https://appskynote.com>

³³<https://yousician.com/>

³⁴<https://makemusic.com/>

³⁵<https://uberchord.com/>

³⁶<https://tonestro.com/>

³⁷<https://riyazapp.com/>

³⁸<https://korg.com/us/products/software/cortosia/>

2.6 Analyzing Salient Performance Moments

The identification of salient performance moments remains an emerging area in music performance research. Salient moments are an important aspect of music performance analysis (MPA) because they comprise a micro-level study of a performer’s expressive choices, like their specific use of tempo and dynamics rather than the broad focus of music information retrieval. Within MPA, salient moments are typically conceptualized in two ways: feature-driven or affect-driven.

Feature-driven saliency is based on deviations from normative expectations—either against the written score or within the performance itself. For instance, a salient moment might be identified at points of high variability in parameters such as dynamics, tempo, or articulation. Juslin (2000) argued that such acoustic cues are systematically manipulated by musicians to communicate emotion, and that high variability in these parameters often signals expressive intent [22]. Similarly, Sloboda (1996) demonstrated that performers’ deviations in tempo and dynamics are not random but serve as deliberate vehicles for emotional communication, again linking variability to expressivity [21]. Subsequent work has reinforced this view, showing that tempo, dynamics, and timbre function as primary cues for emotional perception across instruments such as piano [23], violin [25, 26], and voice [24].

Affect-driven saliency, by contrast, is grounded in human responses to performance. Moments are identified through listener engagement, such as continuous real-time ratings of emotional valence, tension, or expressivity. Techniques like activity analysis capture “exceptional alignment” in these responses, revealing points of shared perceptual significance [180]. For example, Sun et al. (2020) found that structural violations in musical sequences elicited cumulative tension, observable in both behavioral and neural data, underscoring how specific events generate synchronized listener reactions [181]. Experimental platforms have sought to harness this approach to isolate affective moments in performance, though with mixed results [54, 163].

Despite these advances, practical tools for salient moment analysis remain scarce. Musicians currently lack accessible commercial or experimental platforms designed

specifically for this purpose. While existing systems can provide non-real-time feedback from recordings, neither is tailored to identifying salient performance moments or reflection during practice, and most platforms like Sonic Analyser are computationally rather than pedagogically driven. The core challenge lies in bridging the gap between objective acoustic data and its subjective musical meaning, a connection that salient moment analysis ultimately seeks to capture.

2.7 Background Research Summary

The design of MuSA was shaped by the TAD Music Model framework (Section 2.1), which supports musical talent development, and by principles of scaffolding and modeling within learner-centered teaching approaches (Section 2.3). These principles are relevant in both master–apprentice settings and independent practice. Instead of simply signaling correctness, MuSA provides non-prescriptive feedback on salient moments in recorded performances, encouraging learners to engage their own musical understanding and judgment. Moreover, MuSA can support SRL reflection by highlighting key moments in recordings, reducing cognitive load, and making review more focused and efficient. Conceptually, MuSA’s development was further guided by TPCK, highlighting how TEL tools can be designed to address pedagogical goals that would be difficult to meet without technology (Section 2.4). In this way, MuSA seeks to establish a foundation for accessible performance analysis tools that can detect salient moments (Section 2.6), addressing gaps in existing feedback systems (Section 2.5), such as challenges in SRL reflection (Section 2.2.4), while remaining grounded in established principles of musical talent development and TEL design.

Chapter 3

Designing and Implementing MuSA

This chapter presents the design and architecture of MuSA¹, the central application developed for this thesis. Motivated by findings from the background research (Section 2), MuSA was created to address a clear gap in technology-enhanced learning (TEL) for music education: it provides an accessible web application for uploading performance recordings—an effective but underutilized strategy for self-evaluation and reflection—and highlights salient moments of various musical features using low-level audio analysis, thereby streamlining and focusing the process of performance self-reflection.

The following sections discuss the practical implementation of MuSA, including the selected instruments, targeted musical features, feature extraction and variability calculation methods, interface design decisions, and overall system architecture.

3.1 Initial Prototype

Choosing a set of musical aspects. The current MuSA web application (MuSA-V2) is not a direct continuation of the initial prototype (MuSA-V1). Instead, what users encounter today is the second version, developed as an evolution of the first (which I also created). The original prototype was designed with a set of musi-

¹<https://analyzer.appskynote.com>

cal aspects that could be applied broadly to non-fixed-pitch instruments, though its development was particularly focused on the violin. This focus stemmed from the project’s origins: a request from the Royal College of Music (RCM) in London, where a group of violinists had expressed interest in a non-real-time feedback tool that could highlight salient moments in performance. In response, MuSA-V1 emphasized four core aspects of musical expression—timbre, dynamics, pitch, and articulation. For the rest of this chapter, the term *musical aspect* will refer to higher-level musicological characteristics (e.g., timing, intonation), while *musical feature* will denote the corresponding lower-level, quantifiable data extracted from audio to represent that aspect or part of that aspect. Table 1 shows how each aspect was put into practice through lower-level audio feature extraction and how salient sections were identified in MuSA-V1.

Limitations of the original salient moment selection. One limitation of the salient moment selection methods in MuSA-V1 was that only a single moment (or, in the case of articulation, two moments) was chosen as salient. In reality, a musical performance contains multiple salient moments across different musical aspects. Therefore, the definition of salient moments needed to be revised to allow the display of multiple points of interest to the user. Additionally, some musical feature extraction methods, particularly pitch estimation, were prone to inaccuracies in lower-quality audio, and alternative extraction methods needed to be explored. Finally, I needed to clearly define a target audience by selecting a specific set of instruments to focus on and narrow the scope of the project.

MuSA V1 design and limitations. The original wireframe designs for MuSA-V1 and MuSA-V2 were created using Figma², a cloud-based tool for collaboratively designing user interfaces, layouts, and interactive prototypes. Figure 6 shows the resulting wireframes, which were adapted from the design of the SkyNote³ web application, as both applications share the same parent domain. However, while functional, MuSA-V1 had several usability issues. The repeated waveforms added

²<https://figma.com/>

³<https://appskynote.com/>

visual redundancy, and the playable audio waveform was not aligned with the feature curves, making it difficult to map salient moments to the corresponding audio. Highlighted sections on the waveform did not correspond directly to the feature curves, and users could not click on a highlighted moment to play it without opening a separate legend. Variability curves were displayed in a separate tab, but this information was not particularly useful for musicians and added extraneous cognitive load. Furthermore, only one highlighted section per musical aspect was shown, which was a key limitation identified in feedback and needed improvement.

Figure 6: The original MuSA web application based on my Figma wireframe designs.

3.2 Implementing MuSA-V2

To develop MuSA-V2, I narrowed the target instruments of the application. As mentioned in Section 1, variability in musical features such as tempo, dynamics, timbre, and intonation has consistently been shown to signal moments of saliency, often linked to expressive intent [21]. This relationship has been demonstrated across a wide range of instruments, including piano [23], violin [25, 26], and voice [24]. Given this evidence, MuSA-V2 could in principle be applied to many instruments, but I chose to focus on violin and voice. These non-fixed-pitch instruments share

Table 1: Feature extraction and salient moment selection methods (MuSA V1).

Feature	Extraction Method	Saliency Selection
Timbre (MFCCs)	13 Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients extracted with <code>librosa.feature.mfcc</code> using STFT (FFT = 2048, hop = 512).	Sliding window (100 frames, hop = 25). Standard deviation of each MFCC across the window, averaged across coefficients. Sections with highest average std were selected as salient timbre variability.
Loudness (RMS Energy)	Root Mean Square energy from <code>librosa.feature.rms</code> .	Sliding window (100 frames, hop = 25). Standard deviation of RMS values per window. Windows with highest RMS variability were identified as salient loudness sections.
Pitch	Fundamental frequency estimated with <code>librosa.yin</code> (range F3–B6).	Sliding window (100 frames, hop = 25). Pitch values compared to nearest equal-tempered piano note. Mean absolute pitch difference per window calculated. Sections with largest deviation were selected as salient pitch variability.
Articulation (Staccato–Legato)	Combination of RMS derivative and Zero-Crossing Rate (ZCR). RMS difference per window captures amplitude envelope changes; ZCR from <code>librosa.feature.zero_crossing_rate</code> .	For each window, RMS difference and ZCR were standardized across the piece. A weighted combination ($\alpha = 0.5$) produced an articulation level score (0 = staccato, 1 = legato). The two salient sections were defined as the <i>highest</i> (legato) and <i>lowest</i> (staccato) scores.

considerable overlap in key expressive features—such as intonation, vibrato, tempo, and dynamics—and also align with the primary research areas of my supervisor (violin) and co-supervisor (voice).

3.2.1 Selecting Musical Features for MuSA-V2

One of the key pieces of feedback I received from the violinists at the RCM based on MuSA-V1 was that the most important musical aspects to visualize and indicate moments of saliency were dynamics and tempo. Both of these aspects have been supported in the literature as indicators of saliency through variability [21, 25, 26]. Consequently, one of the main goals for the second version was to implement a reliable dynamics and tempo extraction algorithm that could also identify salient moments. This was a challenge in the original version: although an onset envelope was calculated using `librosa.onset.onset_strength`, smoothed with a median filter, and a tempogram was generated with `librosa.feature.tempogram`, estimating and visualizing global and local tempo using `librosa.feature.rhythm tempo` proved unreliable, as the tempo curve could not be accurately inferred from the tempogram. Therefore, I needed to develop a new approach for visualizing tempo over time and select feature extraction algorithms that were robust. Additionally, I had to determine a set of musical aspects for MuSA-V2 that were interesting to implement for both violin and voice, while also narrowing the scope to allow for a complete redevelopment of the MuSA application.

Prioritizing some musical features over others. Not all musical features from MuSA-V1 were carried into V2. While dynamics and pitch remained, timbre and articulation were omitted. Integrating these was possible, but my priority was developing a reliable dynamic and tempo visualization, and the RCM specifically emphasized dynamics and tempo.

Exclusion of timbre. Timbre is generally particularly challenging to extract, as it depends on interactions among multiple lower-level features, including the energy spectrum, short-term transients, and correlations with loudness and pitch [182, 183],

Table 2: Feature extraction methods and criteria for salient moment selection (MuSA V2) with exact parameters.

Musical Aspect	Extraction Method	Saliency Selection
Dynamics	<p>Framewise RMS from <code>librosa.feature.rms</code> and smoothed RMS trace. Parameters: <code>N_FFT = 2048</code>, <code>HOP_LENGTH = 512</code>, smoothing: mean filter with <code>window_percentage = 0.1</code>. Sliding window: <code>WINDOW_PERCENTAGE = 0.05</code>, <code>HOP_PERCENTAGE = 0.0125</code>.</p>	<p>High-variability sections computed using standard deviation over windows. Threshold = 50% of max variability. Returns frame indices and audio-time ranges.</p>
Pitch	<p>Framewise pitch in Hz with confidence, smoothed and filtered by RMS. Extracted using CREPE (<code>EssentiaPitchCREPEmodel</code>, <code>CREPE_HOP_DURATION_SEC = 0.01</code>) or Librosa <code>pyin</code>. Smoothing/segmentation: <code>WINDOW_PERCENTAGE = 0.05</code>, <code>HOP_PERCENTAGE = 0.0125</code>, RMS threshold = 0.01.</p>	<p>High-variability sections computed using <code>calculate_high_variability_sections</code> with <code>is_pitch=True</code>. Sections with largest deviation from nearest equal-tempered piano note were highlighted.</p>
Tempo	<p>Dynamic tempo in BPM using <code>EssentiaBeatTrackerMultiFeature</code>. Smoothed and interpolated to regular time axis. Sample rate = 44100 Hz. Smoothing: median filter. Window fraction: 0.1.</p>	<p>No discrete highlighted sections; returns continuous interpolated tempo trace over time.</p>
Phonation	<p>Frame/window-level phonation class probabilities (breathy, flow, neutral, pressed) using VGGISH embeddings and <code>PHONATION_MODEL</code> (Keras). Window size = 2 frames, hop = 1 frame, frame duration = 0.1 s.</p>	<p>No highlighted sections; returns per-class probability time series.</p>
Vibrato	<p>Per-frame vibrato oscillations around smoothed pitch. Detection uses stable-note identification and oscillation checks. Vibrato extent (amplitude) and rate (Hz) calculated per section. Thresholds: <code>min_sustained_length = 5</code> frames, gap threshold = 5 frames. Extent threshold for highlighting = 1.9. <code>CREPE_HOP_DURATION_SEC = 0.01</code> used for time conversion.</p>	<p>Highlighted sections are frames with extent > 1.9, grouped into consecutive segments. Returns both frame ranges and audio-time ranges.</p>

and so I chose to exclude it from MuSA-V2. Articulation was also left aside due to time constraints. Based on RCM feedback, tempo was added, along with vibrato and phonation mode for voice, guided by the work of my co-supervisor Suvi Hääpä, with vibrato included because it is relevant for both voice and violin. The final set of musical aspects, their extracted audio features, and the method for selecting salient moments are summarized in Table 2.

Implementing dynamic window and hop sizes. An important goal was to ensure that extracted feature curves maintained consistent smoothing and data representation regardless of audio length. For instance, a shorter audio segment using a fixed window size would yield fewer data points than a longer segment, which could lead to noisier curves if the window size were not adjusted. To address this, sliding window and hop sizes were defined as percentages of the audio length where applicable (e.g., for dynamics and pitch), allowing the feature curves to scale proportionally and remain comparable across recordings.

Struggles with identifying variability thresholds. One key piece of feedback from MuSA-V1 was the need to identify multiple salient moments within each audio feature, rather than a single instance. This was addressed by selecting all moments exceeding a specific variability threshold. Alternative approaches could have included selecting the top n most variable sections or applying a threshold to the top n sections, but the implemented method was chosen to avoid excluding potentially interesting moments. The thresholds were determined empirically during development rather than being drawn from existing literature, as few sources provided guidance on precise values. Establishing thresholds based on prior studies represents a clear avenue for improving the robustness and generalizability of the method in future work.

Struggles with tempo extraction. Dynamic tempo tracking was a major challenge for this project. I tested several algorithms, including Essentia's `RhythmExtractor2013` and `TensorflowPredictTempoCNN`. Because voice and violin lack a strong beat, `RhythmExtractor2013` returned few usable points, while `TensorflowPredictTempoCNN`

produced only 2–3 tempo values per segment, especially for short audio, limiting variability analysis. `BeatTrackerMultiFeature` provided more reliable estimates and a higher number of points, so it was selected for implementation. However, the density of points was still insufficient to confidently identify salient moments, so tempo variability was not fully integrated into MuSA-V2. Investigating optimal tempo extraction methods remains an interesting direction for future research, but it fell outside the scope of this thesis, which focused on designing and building the final MuSA-V2 web application.

Implementing voice-specific features. Phonation mode was implemented as an experimental feature in MuSA-V2. Phonation mode describes the manner in which the vocal folds vibrate to produce sound, and changes in phonation throughout a performance can provide valuable insights for singers, particularly in refining expressive techniques and conveying emotion. Suvi Häärrä developed an experimental phonation mode classification model using the Yesiler Phonation dataset, distinguishing four vocal modes: breathy (soft, airy), neutral (standard singing or speech), flow (resonant and clear), and pressed (tense, harsh). I incorporated visualizations of these phonation modes into MuSA with the intention of exploring salient moments based on mode transitions; however, due to time constraints, this functionality was not fully implemented. Nevertheless, all four phonation modes can be visualized in the application, representing a promising direction for future research.

Feature extraction takeaways. Overall, feature extraction was a foundational component in developing MuSA-V2, enabling several successful salient moment visualizations. For example, dynamics produced clear highlighted sections, which may be supported by findings from the evaluation study (Section 4). Pitch extraction using `CREPE` resulted in accurate, smooth pitch curves, and the highlighted sections effectively captured moments of potential intonation—where frequencies deviated from their corresponding equal-tempered piano notes. Vibrato extraction was relatively straightforward, though improvements could be made to identify moments of variability more specifically, rather than relying solely on a fixed threshold. These

and other limitations of salient moment identification, as well as potential alternative approaches, are discussed in Section 5.1.4.

3.2.2 Designing MuSA

In designing MuSA-V2, I considered learner-centered teaching (LCT), self-regulated learning (SRL), and self-directed learning (SDL) principles (Section 2.3), alongside insights from Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK; Section 2.4). TPCK highlighted the importance of identifying topics that are difficult to teach or understand without technology, and of presenting content in ways only possible with technological tools. Accordingly, MuSA-V2 was designed to support both independent and classroom learning, using a web application to make salient moment identification and visual feedback on audio recordings more intuitive. Notably, algorithmically detecting salient moments based on variability is only feasible with such technological support.

MuSA landing page. Based on critiques of MuSA-V1, I aimed to redesign the interface to minimize the number of steps required, reducing extraneous cognitive load for users. For example, users first select one of three instruments on the landing page—violin, voice, or polyphonic (Figure ??). The polyphonic option allows users to analyze recordings with multiple instruments or melodic lines, making the application more broadly accessible. Once an instrument is selected, the available analyses are automatically filtered to those relevant to that instrument. Additionally, audio can be recorded directly within the web application, eliminating the need to use separate platforms, although users can still upload pre-recorded audio if preferred (Figure ??).

Feature-specific visualizations. Additionally, it was important to ensure that the musical aspect visualizations were properly contextualized against their own scales (in a musically relevant way, not just computationally), so users would be able to get meaning out of the results without dealing with the cognitive load associated with trying to interpret very numerical results. For example, pitch (Figure 8b)

and vibrato (Figure 8d) are displayed with a piano-roll background to contextualize frequency within musical notation. Dynamics (Figure 8a) are presented with simple amplitude or BPM scales. The different phonation mode classes (Figure 8c) are shown in separate windows to reflect it's dimensional nature. Vibrato also has separate windows for extent and rate.

Salient moment visualizations. Salient moments, when available for a specific feature, are highlighted and synchronized with the audio waveform. Users can click directly on a highlighted section to play the corresponding audio, providing an immediate connection between the audio and visual elements of the application. Zoom and pan functionality is available across all graphs, ensuring that highlighted sections and audio playback remain aligned at any level of detail.

Other considerations. Users who are unfamiliar with MuSA-V2 require guidance on how to navigate the interface and identify the functions of each button. To address this, information tooltips are toggleable rather than always displayed. Since the application involves sending audio recordings to a server for analysis, users can also choose whether their data is collected via a toggleable consent button (default on). Additionally, feature calculations are cached to avoid redundant computations, improving the overall user experience (discussed further in the following section).

3.3 MuSA System Architecture

Another central consideration in building MuSA-V2 was ensuring accessibility and scalability so that the application could meaningfully impact a wide range of users. To support deployment at scale and simultaneous multi-user access, the system was designed with an architecture comprising four main components. Figure 10 provides an overview of the system architecture.

- **Frontend (React⁴ + Tailwind⁵):** Handles the interactive user interface and renders feature visualizations using D3⁶. The component-based model of React

⁴<https://react.dev/>

⁵<https://tailwindcss.com/>

⁶<https://d3js.org/>

Figure 7: MuSA landing page (top) and file selection or audio recording (bottom).

(a) Dynamics view.

(b) Pitch view.

(c) Phonation view.

(d) Vibrato view.

(e) Tempo view.

Figure 8: Overview of MuSA analysis views.

and the utility-first styling of Tailwind facilitate a flexible and maintainable design.

- **Node.js⁷ API:** Serves as the middle layer between the frontend and the MongoDB⁸ database, managing session metadata and communication.
- **Python Service (Flask⁹ + Gunicorn¹⁰):** Manages all audio-related tasks, including preprocessing, signal and feature extraction, saliency analysis, and caching. Redis¹¹ is used for short-term caching to minimize redundant computation, and audio files are stored locally on the server.
- **Infrastructure (Ubuntu + Nginx¹²):** Handles data management, deployment, and user authentication. Ubuntu is the server with Nginx configured as a reverse proxy. Redis manages caching, MongoDB stores user and session metadata, and JSON Web Tokens (JWT)¹³ secure user sessions.

Explanation of architecture. A separate Python service was used instead of Essentia.js for several reasons. Essentia.js is optimized for short clips (under one minute), while this application targets full performance recordings. Its functionality is also more limited; for example, Essentia’s CREPE pitch-tracking implementation is not available in Essentia.js. Finally, server-side preprocessing—such as trimming silences with Librosa and resampling to the required sample rate—was necessary before analysis. Admittedly, a client-only approach using Essentia.js might have sufficed for a prototype on short audio segments, but this was a lesson learned in hindsight. To ensure user privacy, data is maintained in isolation through the use of Redis-based short-term caching and JWT authentication, ensuring that each user’s uploaded audio and corresponding analyses remain private.

Example user interaction. To better understand how the architecture works, a process diagram of an example user flow is shown in Figure 9. When a musician

⁷<https://nodejs.org/>

⁸<https://mongodb.com/>

⁹<https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/stable/>

¹⁰<https://gunicorn.org/>

¹¹<https://redis.io/>

¹²<https://nginx.org/>

¹³<https://jwt.io/introduction#what-is-json-web-token>

first logs into MuSA, their session is authenticated through a secure JWT connection managed by a Redis cache. Once inside, they select the instrument they want to analyze—for example, violin. The system then prompts them to choose which performance features to focus on, such as pitch stability, loudness, or articulation. After uploading their recording, the Python service processes the audio, extracts the chosen features, calculates saliency, and caches the results to speed up interactions. The user then explores these results in the React frontend, where they can play back their performance, zoom into specific passages, and see salient moments highlighted directly on the timeline. When they are finished, their analysis is stored automatically, with metadata saved in MongoDB and the audio preserved on the server so they can return to it in future practice sessions.

Figure 9: Example user interaction with MuSA.

Figure 10: Process diagram of different MuSA architecture components.

Chapter 4

MuSA Evaluation Study

This chapter describes the methodology and results used to evaluate MuSA’s effectiveness in supporting music practice, self-reflection, performance analysis. Designing the evaluation was not straightforward, as the background literature suggested numerous possible research questions, making it difficult to select a single focus. For instance, an experiment assessing only the utility of salient moments as feedback would require a very different design than one evaluating the full application. Moreover, implementing saliency analysis proved challenging, particularly for features such as tempo, where limited data in the low-level audio feature curves prevented reliable computation of salient moments. Given that MuSA is an experimental tool grounded in psychological principles of musical talent development and teaching practices, and that this thesis focuses on the design and evaluation of MuSA itself, it was appropriate to evaluate the tool comprehensively as applied to self-reflection and self-evaluation rather than isolate the effects of salient moments. The evaluation study follows an approach similar to that used in the TELMI project [184].

Within this broader framework, qualitative data on participants’ perceptions of salient moment detection were considered alongside objective measures of performance improvement and subjective self-ratings. While salient moments primarily reflect expressive intentions and subjective musical saliency, the evaluation study focused on MuSA’s potential to improve or correct performance relative to a reference

(further discussed in Section 5.1.2). Thus, the study conducted within the available time frame addresses one potential use of MuSA—performance correction through reflection—rather than its influence on musical understanding. Nevertheless, the findings contribute to the broader question of how musicians perceive feedback, evaluate their own performances, and reflect, as well as how these perceptions relate to measurable improvement. To guide this evaluation, the study focused on four key questions:

Research Questions

- RQ1:** Does MuSA improve objective performance accuracy across pitch, dynamics, and tempo?
- RQ2:** How do musicians with different talent levels respond to visual feedback?
- RQ3:** How closely do subjective performance ratings align with objective measurements?
- RQ4:** Which musical features benefit most from the feedback provided?

These questions were investigated through a controlled, within-subjects study combining objective audio analysis with participant self-reports, providing a multi-dimensional evaluation of MuSA’s impact. However, this study had clear limitations, particularly in directly assessing the impact of salient moments on improving or correcting musical performance, as discussed in Section 5.1.2.

4.1 Methods

To evaluate MuSA, a web-based testing platform was developed¹ using the same React frontend and Python backend components as the original MuSA application (Chapter 3). The study followed a within-subjects design, adapted from the TELMI evaluation protocol [184, 1], with each participant completing both Control and Feedback (Analyzer Intervention) conditions presented in randomized order to minimize learning effects. Within each condition, participants carried out three rounds targeting the musical features of pitch, dynamics, and tempo, using short

¹<https://analyzer.appskynote.com/testing/>

melodic excerpts from nursery songs to reduce cognitive load (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Workflow of the MuSA evaluation study, adapted from the TELMI protocol [184]. Participants completed both feedback (Analyzer intervention) and control rounds for each of the three musical features. Each round consisted of recording a melodic phrase, providing an initial self-rating, reviewing the recording (with or without MuSA), re-recording, and giving a second self-rating.

In the Feedback condition, participants recorded a phrase, received analyzer feedback, which included the visualization of salient moments discussed in Chapter 3, to highlight areas for potential reflection. In the Control condition, participants followed the same procedure but without access to the analyzer, relying only on self-assessment. For every round (feature), self-perceived performance was rated before and after the intervention on a 7-point Likert scale.

At the end of the study, participants completed a post-test questionnaire providing qualitative feedback on their experience. Questions focused on whether the analyzer helped improve performance, the usefulness of highlighted sections, overall user preferences, and willingness to pay for such a tool. This design allowed for

a direct comparison of performance and self-perception between conditions while controlling for practice and self-evaluation effects.

Stimuli and audio generation. Reference audio stimuli consisted of short melodic phrases from *Mary Had a Little Lamb* (control) and *Twinkle Twinkle Little Star* (feedback), chosen for familiarity and simplicity to minimize cognitive load during the 20–30 minute session. Two different songs were used to avoid carryover effects: because each participant completed both control and feedback rounds, using the same song could have allowed prior exposure to influence performance in the second round. By selecting simple, well-known nursery melodies with minimal complexity, differences between the musical phrases were kept small while still preventing practice effects from one condition affecting the other. Participants vocalized phrases using a neutral syllable (e.g., "la") to isolate pitch, dynamics, and tempo.

Audio files were generated programmatically using Python. MIDI representations of the phrases were created with `pretty_midi`² [185], with tempo and dynamic variations inserted via `mido`³ [186]. MIDI files were rendered to WAV using `FluidSynth`⁴ [187] and standard soundFonts, and silence was trimmed using `librosa`⁵ [188]. Separate WAV files were produced for pitch, dynamics, and tempo conditions to isolate each feature.

Data collection and storage. All audio recordings and participant responses were submitted through the web-based testing platform and securely stored on the SkyNote Linux server. Each audio file was saved in WAV format, and its location was mapped in a MongoDB database. Each participant's data was stored as a separate document, containing only non-identifying information: perceived musical experience level, self-ratings before and after each round, and responses to the post-test questionnaire.

This structured storage approach allowed precise linking between audio recordings,

²<https://github.com/craffel/pretty-midi/>

³<https://mido.readthedocs.io/>

⁴<https://fluidsynth.org/>

⁵<https://librosa.org/doc/>

objective analysis outputs, and subjective ratings. By maintaining this mapping in JSON format within MongoDB, the system ensured that each participant's performance data could be analyzed longitudinally across rounds and conditions while preserving privacy. This setup also facilitated later extraction for statistical analysis and visualization.

Rationale for design choices. The web-based format maximized participant recruitment flexibility despite scheduling and geographical constraints. Familiar nursery melodies reduced cognitive load, ensuring observed effects were attributable to MuSA's feedback rather than task difficulty. Limiting analysis to pitch, dynamics, and tempo maintained a feasible session length while providing meaningful insights. Future studies could extend this paradigm to additional musical features such as vibrato or phonation mode.

4.2 Results

Of the 32 recruited subjects across four musical experience levels (Beginner, Intermediate, Advanced, Professional), 14 met the inclusion criteria for final analysis. The within-subject crossover design allowed each participant to complete both feedback and control conditions, contributing a total of 28 sessions. Participants were retained if they completed the full study, including the questionnaire (Figure 12). Ideally, participants would have been retained only if their recordings were free of audio distortions; however, among those who completed the full experiment, a few recordings contained distortions during the tempo phrase. Excluding these participants would have further weakened the study, so they were retained, and only the distorted tempo recordings were omitted from subsequent analyses. The final sample was composed primarily of Intermediate and Advanced musicians, reflecting the sound and music computing student demographic at Universitat Pompeu Fabra. As a result, the analyses are most representative of the *Competence* and *Expertise* stages of the TAD Music Model.

By mapping participant experience levels onto the TAD Music Model, the evalu-

Figure 12: Distribution of the 14 participants retained for final analysis across musical experience levels: 1 Beginner, 7 Intermediate, 5 Advanced, and 1 Professional. When mapped onto the TAD Music Model (Aptitude, Competence, Expertise, Transformational Achievement), the sample reflects a concentration in the *Competence* (Intermediate) and *Expertise* (Advanced) stages, aligning with the sound and music computing student demographic at Universitat Pompeu Fabra.

ation design allows for a more direct comparison between performance outcomes and underlying psychological and cognitive processes. Although familiar labels such as Intermediate and Advanced were used to describe participants, these categories correspond to the *Competence* and *Expertise* stages of the TAD framework. This mapping makes it possible to interpret differences in self-perception and performance not only in terms of musical skill but also through the lens of developmental processes in expertise acquisition. For instance, participants at the *Competence* stage may rely more heavily on external feedback to structure practice and refine their playing, whereas those at the *Expertise* stage may integrate feedback differently, drawing on internalized strategies and prior knowledge.

4.2.1 Objective Performance Metrics

Objective performance was derived from computational analysis of recorded audio using the same feature extraction algorithms implemented in MuSA. Pitch was esti-

mated using CREPE [189], dynamics were quantified via Root Mean Square (RMS) energy using the `feature.rms` function from `librosa`, and tempo was measured using Essentia’s `BeatTrackerMultiFeature` algorithm [190, 191].

Participant recordings under control and feedback conditions were compared with reference performances. To account for temporal variability, dynamic time warping (DTW) aligned performances for point-by-point comparison, a technique that has been proven to work effectively for aligning audio signals under a variety of conditions [192, 193]. Because pitch, dynamics, and tempo operate on different scales, analyses were conducted in three complementary ways: raw RMSE values for unprocessed deviations, baseline-standardized percentage improvements for within-subject changes, and z-score standardization to allow cross-feature comparison and effect size evaluation. Effect sizes were calculated using Cohen’s d , which quantifies the standardized mean difference between groups, providing a measure of practical significance beyond statistical tests. This approach provides both feature-specific and integrative perspectives on the impact of MuSA feedback.

Raw RMSE results. As shown in Figure 13, raw RMSE values before and after the intervention displayed considerable spread across all three musical features. Tempo was the only feature with a statistically significant effect, with the feedback group performing worse than the control group ($p = 0.0096$, $d = 0.97$; Appendix Table 4). Pitch and dynamics showed no significant condition effects ($p > 0.32$, $|d| < 0.27$), though the wide variability illustrated in the boxplots suggests substantial individual differences that may have masked smaller effects. Taken together, these results suggest that tempo was most sensitive to disruption from feedback, while pitch and dynamics remained inconclusive at this level of analysis (see Appendix Table 5).

Experience-level analyses further clarified these raw RMSE patterns. As shown in Figure 14, intermediate musicians showed moderate effects for pitch ($\Delta = -77.05$, $d = -0.37$), small effects for dynamics ($\Delta = 0.0038$, $d = 0.15$), and moderate effects for tempo ($\Delta = 5.71$, $d = 0.38$), all corresponding to nonsignificant results

Figure 13: Raw RMSE performance across three musical features—pitch (Hz), dynamics (RMS), and tempo (BPM)—before and after the intervention for both control and feedback groups. Box plots display medians, quartiles, and outliers for each condition. Lower RMSE values indicate better performance. Sample sizes ranged from 9–14 participants per condition. Results show substantial spread across participants, with tempo most clearly disrupted by feedback, while pitch and dynamics show no clear condition-level effects.

Figure 14: Change in RMSE for pitch, dynamics, and tempo across four musician experience levels (After – Before), with negative values indicating improved performance. No statistically significant effects were observed for condition or timing (all $p > 0.05$). Beginner and Professional groups had very small sample sizes ($n=2$), and although some large effect sizes were seen (e.g., Intermediate tempo $d = 0.94$, Beginner dynamics $d = 7.58$), these results are likely influenced by high variability.

($p > 0.09$). Advanced musicians exhibited small-to-moderate effects across features (pitch: $\Delta = 14.65$, $d = 0.33$; dynamics: $\Delta = -0.0048$, $d = -0.16$; tempo: $\Delta = 9.54$, $d = 0.59$), again nonsignificant ($p > 0.32$). Beginner and professional groups had extremely small sample sizes, producing highly variable and unstable effect sizes (e.g., Beginner dynamics Feedback vs Control: $d = 7.58$) that were also nonsignificant. Overall, although no comparisons reached statistical significance, the effect sizes and mean differences suggest that responses to feedback varied by experience, with

intermediate musicians tending toward moderate improvements and beginners/professionals showing high variability and extreme but unreliable effects (Appendix Tables 6-8).

Baseline-standardized improvements. To account for baseline performance differences, percent improvement scores were calculated for each feature (Appendix Table 9, Figure 15). Across all participants, feedback showed a modest relative advantage for dynamics (+14.1 pp compared to control), but no benefit for pitch (-10.1 pp) and a marked detriment for tempo (-110.3 pp). None of these contrasts reached statistical significance ($p > 0.28$), reflecting both limited sample size and high inter-individual variability, but the pattern suggests that feedback selectively influenced temporal control while offering limited support for pitch or dynamic accuracy.

Figure 15: Percent improvement from individual baselines across pitch, dynamics, and tempo. Violin plots with overlaid box plots show percentage change relative to pre-intervention baseline. Horizontal dashed line indicates no change. Statistical markers show effect sizes and p-values (all non-significant).

When analyzed by musical experience level (Appendix Table 10, Figure 16), no statistically significant subgroup effects were observed. Descriptively, intermediate musicians showed the largest positive differences across features (dynamics +27.1%, tempo +116.7%, pitch +2.9%), while advanced musicians' outcomes trended closer to zero or negative (pitch -28.5%, tempo -392.0%, dynamics +0.3%). Beginners and professionals contributed very limited data, with single cases per condition, making their results uninterpretable.

Figure 16: Percent improvement from individual baselines by musical experience level (Beginner, Intermediate, Advanced, Professional). Violin plots compare feedback and control groups within each category; all comparisons were non-significant. Dashed line shows no change from baseline.

Z-score standardized comparisons. To account for cross-feature scale differences, RMSE values were z-score standardized against baseline distributions. As shown in Figure 17, feedback was associated with a small positive shift in dynamics (+0.41 SD, $d = 0.41$) and a negligible effect for pitch (-0.17 SD, $d = 0.16$), while tempo showed a small detrimental shift (-0.43 SD, $d = 0.43$). None of these differences reached statistical significance ($p > 0.28$). More summary statistics, including effect sizes and p-values, are provided in Appendix Tables 11–12.

Figure 17: Z-score standardized improvement by feature (Pitch, Dynamics, Tempo) for control and feedback conditions. Violin plots show distributions, with overlaid box plots for median and quartiles. Positive values indicate above-baseline improvement. All comparisons were non-significant ($p > 0.28$).

When broken down by musical experience (Figure 18), no subgroup effects reached statistical significance, though descriptive differences appeared. Intermediate musi-

Figure 18: Z-score standardized improvement by experience level (Beginner, Intermediate, Advanced, Professional) for Pitch, Dynamics, and Tempo. Violin plots show distributions for control and feedback conditions. Statistical annotations indicate effect sizes (d) and p -values. Most differences were non-significant, highlighting heterogeneity in responses across experience levels.

icians showed the largest positive shifts (dynamics $+0.78$ SD, tempo $+0.46$ SD, pitch $+0.05$ SD), while advanced musicians tended toward neutral or negative changes (pitch -0.46 SD, tempo -1.54 SD, dynamics $+0.01$ SD). Beginner and professional participants contributed only isolated data points, limiting interpretability. Overall, these standardized analyses suggest potential variation in feedback effects by experience level, but given small samples and non-significant tests, these trends should be considered exploratory.

4.2.2 Perceived Performance Metrics

To evaluate participants' subjective experience of improvement, self-ratings on pitch, dynamics, and tempo were collected before and after practice sessions under control (no feedback) and feedback conditions. Paired t -tests were conducted within each condition to assess changes over time, while between-condition comparisons (feedback vs. control) were performed on pre- and post-practice ratings. Effect sizes (Cohen's d) were calculated to quantify the magnitude of observed differences. This approach allowed for examining both overall perceived performance changes and variations across musical experience levels, providing a complementary perspective to objective performance metrics.

Overall, participants' self-ratings varied by feature and condition (Figure 19). For

Figure 19: Comparison of self-rated performance before and after the intervention across different musical experience levels. Each subplot represents one musical feature (pitch, dynamics, tempo). Box colors distinguish 'Before' and 'After' ratings, highlighting changes in perceived performance across experience levels.

pitch, perceived improvements were minimal, with feedback producing a small average increase (+0.15 points, $p = 0.656$, $d = -0.122$), indicating little impact of the feedback tool. Dynamics showed the largest perceived gains, increasing on average by +1.00 points with feedback, which was highly significant ($p = 0.0009^{***}$, $d = -1.003$). Tempo improvements were less consistent: feedback led to a moderate increase (+0.58 points, $p = 0.089$, $d = -0.563$), while practice alone produced a slightly larger improvement (+0.94 points, $p = 0.0106^*$), suggesting general practice contributed to tempo perception more than feedback (Appendix Table 13).

Considering musical experience (Figure 21), differences emerged across features. For pitch, advanced participants showed the largest perceived improvement with feedback (+0.60), though this change was not statistically significant ($p = 0.4766$, $d = 0.14$), whereas beginners showed inconsistent changes. Dynamics benefited all experience levels, with beginners and intermediates showing the largest positive shifts (+2.00 and +1.29 points with feedback, respectively); only intermediates reached statistical significance ($p = 0.0004^{***}$, $d = 0.92$), while changes for beginners

Figure 20: Self-reported performance ratings by musical experience across three features: (A) Pitch, (B) Dynamics, (C) Tempo. Box plots show ratings before (light purple) and after (medium purple) practice, combining control (no feedback) and experimental (feedback) conditions. Medians (thick line), interquartile range (box), and outliers (circles) are shown. Experience levels: Beg = Beginner, Int = Intermediate, Adv = Advanced, Pro = Professional.

Figure 21: Mean perceived improvement (after minus before) by musical experience and intervention type for (A) Pitch, (B) Dynamics, (C) Tempo. Dark purple bars indicate feedback, light purple bars indicate control. Positive values reflect improvement, negative values reflect decline. Numbers above bars show exact values ≥ 0.01 . Horizontal line at zero indicates no change.

(+2.00) and advanced participants (+0.40) were not significant. Tempo improvements were most notable in the control condition for beginners (+3.00, $p = 0.011^*$), with smaller gains from feedback observed in other groups (intermediate: +1.05, $p = 0.089$; advanced: +0.00, $p = 1.0$). Overall, perception of dynamics performance improved with MuSA, particularly for intermediate participants, while perceived improvements in pitch were limited and tempo gains likely reflected general practice effects rather than MuSA's reflective feedback (Appendix Table 14).

4.2.3 Self-Awareness Metrics

Self-awareness reflects the degree to which participants' perceptions of their own performance align with objectively measured outcomes. To quantify this, perceived improvements were compared with actual performance changes using Pearson correlation coefficients. Correlations were calculated between self-reported ratings and RMSE values, between perceived improvement and percentage improvement, and between helpfulness ratings and actual performance gains, providing a primary index of self-assessment accuracy.

For direct comparison across scales, objective improvements were rescaled to approximately match the Likert range by dividing by 7. Absolute self-awareness error was then computed as the absolute difference between subjective and scaled objective improvements, with lower values indicating greater accuracy. Condition-level differences were assessed using Mann–Whitney U tests, independent t-tests, and Cohen's d to quantify effect sizes.

Overall metrics. Comparing subjective self-ratings to objective measures across pitch, dynamics, and tempo revealed generally weak correlations, indicating poor self-awareness among participants. Overall, the Control group showed $r = -0.027$ ($p = 0.874$, $n = 36$) and the Feedback group $r = -0.182$ ($p = 0.304$, $n = 34$), with neither reaching statistical significance. Feature-specific analyses mirrored this pattern: for pitch, $r = 0.089$ (Control) and $r = -0.160$ (Feedback), $p = 0.062$; for dynamics, $r = -0.267$ (Control) and $r = 0.101$ (Feedback), $p = 0.148$; and for tempo, $r = 0.317$ (Control) and $r = -0.363$ (Feedback), $p = 0.694$. None of these correlations were statistically significant, suggesting that participants' perceived improvements did not reliably align with objective performance across features or conditions (Appendix Table 15).

To further characterize self-awareness, participants' assessments were classified into four categories: **Accurate**, **Overconfident**, **Underconfident**, and **Somewhat Inaccurate**. Classification was based on the difference between subjective improvement and scaled objective improvement. A response was considered Accurate if this

Figure 22: Correlation scores between self-ratings and objective performances for three musical features (pitch, dynamics, and tempo).

Figure 23: Scatter plots examining the relationship between participants' perceived improvement (subjective self-ratings) and actual performance improvement (objective measurements) across three musical features: pitch, dynamics, and tempo. Control participants are shown in orange, and feedback participants in blue. The red dashed line indicates perfect self-awareness.

absolute difference was ≤ 1 , accounting for typical perceptual noise. Overconfident responses reflected large positive subjective changes despite performance decline (subjective improvement > 1 and objective improvement $< -5\%$), whereas Underconfident responses reflected negative self-ratings despite substantial improvement (subjective improvement < -1 and objective improvement $> 10\%$). Remaining cases were labeled Somewhat Inaccurate, capturing moderate misalignments with-

out extreme bias.

Applying this classification to 70 performance assessments yielded 49 Somewhat Inaccurate cases (70.0%), 16 Accurate cases (22.9%), 5 Overconfident cases (7.1%), and 0 Underconfident cases (0.0%), highlighting generally limited metacognitive accuracy. Figure 23 visualizes these results, with a red dashed line representing perfect self-awareness (where perceived and actual improvements align). Data points are dispersed across all quadrants, illustrating participants' overall difficulty in accurately judging their own performance changes.

By condition. To further examine self-awareness, subjective–objective correlations were compared across the control (no feedback) and feedback conditions. Although there were only 14 unique participants, each subject could contribute up to three assessments per condition (pitch, dynamics, tempo), yielding a larger pool of datapoints. Not all participants completed every feature assessment, and some assessments were excluded during data quality checks, leading to a final total of 36 control assessments and 34 feedback assessments. In the control group, six participants provided two assessments and eight participants provided three, resulting in 14 pitch, 14 dynamics, and 8 tempo datapoints. In the feedback group, one participant provided only a single assessment, six provided two, and seven provided three, resulting in 13 pitch, 14 dynamics, and 7 tempo datapoints.

The control group showed a near-zero correlation between subjective and objective improvement ($r = -0.027$, $n = 36$), while the feedback group demonstrated a slightly more negative relationship ($r = -0.182$, $n = 34$). Absolute self-awareness errors were also higher in the feedback group ($M = 7.16$, $SD = 16.96$) compared to the control group ($M = 4.03$, $SD = 6.17$). However, neither group difference reached significance (Mann–Whitney $U = 583.0$, $p = .738$; independent $t = -1.038$, $p = .303$), and the effect size was small ($d = -0.248$). Feature-level analyses suggested that pitch self-awareness was marginally poorer in the feedback condition ($p = .062$), while dynamics and tempo showed no reliable group differences (Appendix Table 16).

By experience level. Figure 24 shows how patterns of self-awareness varied across levels of musical experience. Intermediate musicians demonstrated moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.244$; $n = 35$; $p = 0.16$), suggesting some alignment between their perceived and actual improvement. Beginners ($r = -0.293$; $n = 6$; $p = 0.57$) and advanced musicians ($r = -0.437$; $n = 24$; $p = 0.033$) exhibited inverse self-awareness, tending to misjudge their progress in ways that ran counter to objective measures. Professional musicians showed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.694$; $n = 5$; $p = 0.19$), although the small sample size limits the reliability of this observation. Overall, only the negative correlation for advanced musicians reached statistical significance (Appendix Table 17).

Figure 24: Correlation scores between self-ratings and objective performances across measured experience levels.

4.2.4 Sentiment Analysis

Participant feedback from the post-study questionnaire was analyzed to assess subjective impressions of MuSA, both overall and specifically regarding users' perceptions of highlighted (salient) moment feedback. Sentiment analysis quantified the positivity or negativity of responses both by question (experience, improvement, highlights, payment) and overall. Responses were scored using a lexicon-based ap-

proach and, when available, VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner) compound scores. Word frequency and word cloud visualizations highlighted common themes, and correlations between sentiment scores and participant characteristics (e.g., musical experience, practice time) were examined to explore links between subjective impressions and behavior.

Table 3: Questionnaire items and corresponding labels.

Label	Question
experience	How was your experience with the audio analyzer feedback tool? What did you like or dislike about it? How did you feel about your music performance in using versus not using the audio analyzer?
improvement	Do you think the audio analyzer feedback tool helped improve your performances of the reference audios? If so, how? If not, why not?
highlights	Were the highlighted areas in the feedback tool visualization helpful for the given audio features? If so, how? If not, why not?
payment	Would you pay for a similar audio analysis feedback service? If so, how much?

Lexicon-based approach. Overall, sentiment was positive across all questionnaire items, with a mean lexicon-based sentiment of 0.223 (N=56). By question (Table 3), participants reported highest positivity for experience (mean=0.308) and highlights (mean=0.242), followed by improvement (mean=0.186) and payment (mean=0.156). Common themes in comments included clarity of feedback, usefulness for practice, and engagement, while negative comments mainly addressed limitations such as lack of real-time feedback or minor misalignment issues. Representative participant quotes further illustrate these points (Appendix Table 18).

Representative comments reflected generally positive experiences with the tool’s guidance on pitch, dynamics, and tempo, while highlighting areas for improvement such as real-time responsiveness and alignment between visual feedback and performed audio. Payment willingness varied, with some participants willing to pay for the tool if it provided demonstrable benefits or real-time features, and others expressing little interest.

scatter plot (Figure 26). Across questions, Pearson correlations between lexicon sentiment and VADER compound scores ranged from moderate to high, confirming the robustness of overall positive sentiment patterns (Appendix Table 19).

No strong correlations were observed between sentiment and numeric participant metrics (e.g., practice time, musical experience level, first condition), likely due to limited sample overlap. Overall, these results indicate that participants reacted positively to the audio analysis tool, particularly regarding clarity of feedback and helpfulness of highlighted performance segments (salient moment analysis), while noting minor usability limitations.

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.1 Discussion

This thesis investigates how technology-enhanced learning (TEL) tools can support musical development through non-real-time feedback on recorded performances. Central to this exploration is MuSA, a fully developed audio analysis tool that implements feature-driven salient moment analysis and has been evaluated to assess its effectiveness and contextualize its role within the broader landscape of music practice technologies. By synthesizing concepts from music talent development, cognitive principles, and learner-centered teaching strategies with the specific design and evaluation of MuSA, this discussion presents key findings, considers the limitations of the study, and outlines directions for future research.

5.1.1 Integrating Theory into Practice

The development of MuSA was informed by a core set of pedagogical and cognitive principles. The Talent-Development-in-Achievement-Domains (TAD) Music Model, for example, provided a framework for understanding how different stages of musical talent require different kinds of support. While MuSA does not explicitly focus on teaching or developing expressive skills, it provides a flexible, feature-driven analytical framework that allows musicians to explore and act upon their own interpretive

decisions. By highlighting salient performance sections and showing feature-level deviations in pitch, dynamics, or timing, MuSA enables learners to target these areas for particular outcomes based on their intended expression. In this way, the tool supports self-directed learning (SDL) and learner-centered teaching (LCT) principles, giving students ownership over how they analyze and refine their performances, and allowing expressive goals to emerge as a product of informed, feature-driven practice rather than prescriptive instruction.

The concept of salience analysis was central to MuSA's design. Rather than prescribing how a musician should express themselves, MuSA identifies moments in a performance that deviate from feature-specific expected norms. These norms are computed relative to the uploaded performance itself. For example, a fast dynamic change or high variability in dynamics compared to surrounding sections would be highlighted. For pitch, salient moments correspond to deviations from the expected note within a 12-semitone scale, and vibrato sections are detected and highlighted when they exceed a defined threshold. Importantly, these expected norms are inherently flexible and can be adapted based on a user's goals, cultural context, or notation preferences.

As a point of comparison, one of the goals of TELMI, the parent project of MuSA, was to provide real-time visual feedback on timbre, a feature that is inherently subjective. The success of TELMI demonstrates that meaningful feedback can be provided even when the underlying musical attribute is difficult to quantify, and that it is both acceptable and expected for TEL tools to interpret measurements or classifications of subjective data in order to offer targeted feedback to learners [1]. Similarly, by defining salient moments through a specific, feature-driven approach, MuSA helps narrow the learner's focus during practice. Instead of having to consider all possible ways a moment could be interpreted as salient, the tool provides one concrete lens for attention, guiding practice in a manageable and structured way. This does not preclude the use of other techniques, such as human-guided feedback based explicitly on affect, which could be applied alongside MuSA to capture aspects of performance that extend beyond feature-based salient moment analysis.

5.1.2 Evaluating MuSA: Demand, Limitations, and Outcomes

The evaluation study was an essential step in validating the concepts behind MuSA. Despite its limitations—a small sample size with few usable data, the use of different microphones, and the remote, asynchronous nature of the study—it produced a number of findings. Subjective feedback from the post-study questionnaire indicated that participants perceived MuSA as a potentially helpful tool, particularly for improving awareness of dynamics. This aligns with the overall positive sentiment expressed in the sentiment analysis, where participants appreciated the clarity and usefulness of highlighted salient moments. Minor usability issues were noted, including lack of real-time responsiveness and occasional misalignment between visual feedback and actual performance, highlighting opportunities for refining the user experience.

Objective performance metrics. The objective performance metrics revealed a more nuanced picture of MuSA’s impact across skill levels and musical features. Dynamics consistently benefited the most from feedback, whereas pitch improvements were minimal and tempo outcomes were inconsistent. Experience level further moderated these effects: intermediate musicians, corresponding to the *Competence* stage of the TAD model, often demonstrated measurable gains, while advanced musicians, corresponding to the *Expertise* stage, sometimes showed neutral or slightly negative changes, particularly for tempo. Although these trends were not statistically significant, they point to the expertise reversal effect, whereby feedback methods that benefit less experienced learners may disrupt the performance strategies of experts [194, 195, 196, 197, 198]. This also aligns with Colombo (2017), who suggested that young music students benefit from greater teacher support and monitoring, while more advanced students gain more from developing metacognitive skills such as reflecting on their learning strategies [199].

Perceived performance and self-awareness. Analysis of perceived performance revealed that participants reported the greatest improvement for dynamics, moderate improvement for tempo, and minimal change for pitch. Notably, some tempo

improvements appeared to result from practice alone rather than tool-mediated feedback, emphasizing the importance of distinguishing intrinsic learning effects from the influence of MuSA. Self-assessment metrics demonstrated generally weak alignment with objective performance, suggesting limited self-awareness. Intermediate musicians showed modestly better self-assessment accuracy, whereas advanced musicians were often inversely aligned with their measured outcomes. These findings align with research on musician self-awareness, which suggests that learners' self-assessments can be inaccurate [200]. Overall, poor self-assessment may directly reflect of a challenge in the self-reflection phase of the SRL cycle. They also highlight the complex interaction between experience, feature type, and self-evaluation in music practice, indicating that MuSA could be enhanced with metacognitive prompts to support more accurate performance judgments.

Taken together, these results indicate that MuSA may selectively support musical practice as most effective for dynamics and for learners at intermediate skill levels, while advanced learners may experience neutral or slightly negative effects. Subjective impressions suggest that the tool successfully directs attention to salient performance moments, although future iterations could benefit from improvements in interactivity and alignment of visual feedback with audio. These insights underscore the importance of combining subjective and objective measures when evaluating digital feedback tools and point toward practical design considerations, including feature-specific guidance and adaptive feedback calibrated to experience level.

Limitations. One of the main limitations of the MuSA evaluation study was that it tested the application as a whole, rather than isolating the effect of salient moment highlighting itself. Participants were asked to perform a task with the full analyzer and without it, meaning that only general statements about MuSA's overall utility can be made, rather than conclusions specifically about the impact of indicating salient moments versus displaying raw feature curves alone. This distinction is important, particularly because tempo saliency analysis was not implemented due to algorithmic limitations. Interestingly, this provides a natural comparison: dynamics feedback showed a more consistently positive trend on performance, whereas tempo

feedback—absent in the final version—might have had a markedly negative effect if implemented, illustrating a potential differential impact of feature type on practice outcomes.

Another limitation is that the study did not specifically assess whether MuSA improves a musician’s expressive intent or ability to create expressive performance moments, and moreover, didn’t explicitly confirm its use as a reflective, non-corrective, post-performance tool. Testing this functionality and acquiring more qualitative data regarding its reflective potential would have required recruiting both highly skilled musicians capable of intentionally manipulating expressive parameters and less experienced participants, as well as facilitating extended, carefully structured practice sessions—constraints that exceeded the available thesis timeline, especially given the time-intensive process of developing the MuSA web application itself.

Additionally, the choice of two simple pieces based on melodic segments from common children’s songs may not have been adequate to evaluate the use of MuSA across all stages of the TAD Music Model. For example, the simplicity of the reference audios may have been trivial for advanced participants, also potentially explaining the inverse relationship between expertise level and improvement. Ideally, the evaluation would be using different music pieces relevant to each participant, but this would have introduced an extra variable, perhaps overcomplicating the evaluation study based on the given thesis timeframe.

Finally, the small usable sample size (14 out of 32 participants) limits the generalizability of the findings. Most observed effects were not statistically significant, making it difficult to draw definitive conclusions. Nevertheless, the study revealed intriguing patterns regarding feature-specific and experience-dependent effects of feedback, providing a valuable benchmark and setting the stage for future research and iterations of MuSA or similar non-real-time feedback applications.

Implications. Nevertheless, the feedback from participants and the initial request from RCM musicians highlight a clear, unmet need for non-real-time feedback tools that engage with practice self-reflection. Existing tools, such as Sonic Analyser and

Audacity, are powerful but lack pedagogical orientation and the ability to abstract raw audio into meaningful, musically salient moments. MuSA, therefore, represents a promising approach, but further research with a larger, more diverse participant sample is needed to validate its pedagogical impact and refine which types of salient moment analysis are most effective across skill levels.

5.1.3 Independent Practice and Learner Implications

Developing MuSA was an important step in exploring how technology can enhance independent practice, which is often unstructured and lacks expert feedback. As discussed in Section 2.2.5, independent practice requires self-regulated learning (SRL) skills, such as self-reflection and goal-setting, which are challenging for learners without consistent teacher guidance. By highlighting salient moments, MuSA aims to scaffold the self-monitoring process, directing a learner's attention to specific points for reflection and experimentation. This supports a cycle of reflective learning that is crucial for developing self-directed learning skills.

This potential benefit is particularly important given the challenges learners face with metacognition, or the awareness of their own thinking and learning processes. The self-awareness metrics from this study suggest that metacognitive accuracy is a significant hurdle in independent practice, as participants across the board showed generally poor alignment between their subjective perceptions and objective performance outcomes ($r = -0.122$). This finding aligns with broader research indicating that learners often struggle to accurately assess their own performance [201, 202]. Interestingly, while the self-evaluation study suggested that intermediate (*Competence*) musicians were moderately accurate in judging their own performances after using MuSA, this pattern may partly reflect self-selection bias: individuals identifying as intermediate may approach self-assessment and reflection more cautiously and analytically, whereas those identifying as advanced (*Expertise*) may rely more on internalized, emotionally driven expectations of how they should perform at their level.

Nevertheless, this overall lack of self-awareness underscores the importance of ex-

ternal tools in supporting independent learning. Since metacognitive skills are not always innate, technology can provide a concrete foundation for reflection, whether through binary correct/incorrect feedback that highlights salient moments (as MuSA does) or by identifying performance characteristics such as affect. With respect to improving performance self-awareness (which was not MuSA's primary goal), the present study did not reveal clear gains from using the analyzer tool, but it is difficult to draw definitive conclusions. Self-awareness typically develops gradually within scaffolding frameworks and dialogic learning contexts, where sustained external feedback such as guidance from a tutor supports its growth over time. It is possible that extended use of a tool like MuSA could contribute to shaping self-awareness, particularly as study participants were also managing the cognitive load of learning how to use the system, which may have influenced self-awareness results.

5.1.4 MuSA's Limitations and Future Directions

Expanding feature-driven saliency analyses. MuSA's current approach to saliency analysis is primarily feature-driven, focusing on identifying moments where objective musical features—such as pitch, dynamics, or tempo—show significant variability relative to an established performance norm. During the implementation phase, however, several roadblocks emerged. For example, highlighting moments of high tempo variability proved difficult because the amount of tempo data extracted from a piece was much lower compared to pitch or dynamics. In addition, developing a signal processing algorithm that could consistently handle shorter audio segments within the given time constraints was not feasible. As a result, tempo variability could not be highlighted as reliably as other features. Future work should therefore prioritize implementing more robust algorithms for tempo analysis, as the MuSA framework already supports such functionality and only requires the right computational approach.

Beyond tempo, other features present opportunities for further refinement. For instance, MuSA currently identifies vibrato moments using a fixed threshold. While this method works, it misses the expressive nuance conveyed through changes in

vibrato rate and extent. Yang et al. (2013) demonstrated that variability in vibrato can signal expressive intent [25], suggesting that saliency detection could be improved by tracking vibrato variability across a performance rather than applying a hard cutoff. This would allow the tool to capture more abstract and musically meaningful performance moments.

Similarly, phonation mode has been implemented for voice, but its role in saliency remains an open question. Is it the transition from one phonation mode to another that creates salience? Or is it sustained use of a particular mode in contrast to surrounding material? Investigating such questions would not only refine how salience is operationalized but also expand the interpretive power of MuSA in analyzing expressive vocal performance.

Integrating more features. A missed opportunity in MuSA was also to detect salient moments through timbre, for example, as timbre is one of the primary mechanisms through which we detect emotion in music [43, 24]. This could, for example, involve detecting and displaying variable moments in timbre related low-level features like spectral centroid and flux to users and letting them interpret musical meaning and understanding from these highlighted areas based on their intention. Though the original prototype for MuSA included highlighting the most variable timbre section based on MFCCs, the final version did not include it for timing and scheduling reasons based on workload and the design of the application itself.

Integrating affect-driven saliency analysis. Moreover, a complementary approach to the feature-based one could involve affect-driven saliency analysis, such as activity analysis [180]. In this case, a model could be trained to identify key moments across different instrumental performances—starting, for instance, with voice and violin—by detecting points where listeners consistently perceive a particular affective quality, such as sadness or happiness.

Integrating activity analysis would also align more explicitly with the TDPK Music Framework (Section 2.4), which emphasizes that musical experiences are inseparable from their expressive character. Compared to feature-driven saliency analysis,

this approach would provide more prescriptive feedback about potential affect and musical expression. At the same time, as the evaluation study suggests, such prescriptive feedback on expressive sections might be most effective for learners who are still developing these skills, while more advanced musicians may benefit less from this type of guidance (a potential reverse expert effect as previously mentioned).

Need for musical understanding. This points to another potential limitation of the tool: effectively interpreting the feedback provided by MuSA likely requires a certain level of musical understanding, typically at the intermediate level or beyond. For beginners, an explicitly prescriptive, task-level feedback tool may be more effective, as suggested by the McPherson et al. feedback matrix [130]. At the same time, feedback must be appropriately tailored so as not to interfere with the self-regulatory abilities that intermediate and advanced learners have developed. In this sense, the fact that MuSA is not overly prescriptive and instead requires some interpretive background knowledge may, from the learner's perspective, be considered a benefit rather than a drawback.

Musa as a web application. One explicit benefit of MuSA is its fully online format. Users do not need to download software, create an account, or navigate complex setup processes. The range of available analyses is intentionally limited, which some might view as a drawback since users cannot access an extensive menu of options or review past uploads. However, this simplicity also reduces barriers to use: learners can either record directly within the application or upload existing audio files and receive visual feedback immediately. While tools such as Sonic Visualiser offer sophisticated analysis capabilities, they were not designed with a pedagogical audience in mind, but rather for computational research, and are therefore underutilized in performance review contexts. By contrast, MuSA's streamlined design makes it more accessible for musicians, minimizing cognitive load compared to the steep learning curve of downloading, configuring, and interpreting results from specialized software like Sonic Visualiser.

Current architectural limitations. Currently, MuSA functions as a minimum viable product. While it can handle a large number of simultaneous user interactions through its Redis-based setup, it is not yet optimized for large-scale deployment. Current constraints include shared server resources, redundancy from the dual Node.js and Flask services—which could be streamlined by consolidating database calls into the Python service—and reliance on local file storage, which would benefit from a cloud-based solution for improved scalability and resilience. All collected data is stored directly on the server, which has limited capacity. While this setup allows data to be retained, it also introduces the challenge of managing and maintaining growing storage demands. In practice, this means that someone must periodically transfer the collected audio files to an external drive, a process that can be both time-consuming and inconvenient. Additionally, the development stack uses Create React App, which has been deprecated; migrating to Vite would modernize the build process and improve efficiency. Addressing these redundancies and infrastructure limitations is a priority for future versions, but due to time constraints, a fully commercial-level tool was not feasible. Nevertheless, MuSA provides a functional foundation for delivering salience-based analysis to learners, enabling non-real-time performance feedback that can inform future iterations and related projects.

Integrating written notation. In terms integration with notation, MuSA does not currently employ score alignment with performances, which some may view as a limitation. Score alignment, however, comes with its own drawback: it requires the performer to have a notated score for comparison, which may not always be available or relevant. MuSA deliberately avoids this feature because its focus is on the performance itself, privileging the performer’s expressive intent over adherence to notation, and distancing itself from the binary correct/incorrect prescriptions seen in real-time feedback tools like Yousician. That said, score alignment can also offer valuable insights into performance and expressive intent, and several studies highlight its usefulness. Future iterations of MuSA could therefore integrate score alignment as an optional feature to enhance salient-moment analysis, particularly

when key score events are involved. Such integration could even allow users to set variability targets based on the score or receive feedback framed in more traditional musical terms. Importantly, incorporating score alignment may be more feasible in MuSA’s non-real-time setting, since real-time score following remains technically challenging to implement reliably.

Performance-to-performance alignment. Another feature originally intended for MuSA but not implemented due to time and resource constraints was direct comparison to a target audio recording. This would have been valuable because the reference performance itself contains feature-driven salient moments that could be extracted and directly compared to those in the user’s recording. While comparative performance analysis is already used in the field, there remains a need for more sophisticated approaches beyond simple error detection [203]. In this sense, MuSA could eventually be expanded to compare salient moments between a student’s performance and a reference recording, offering feedback that is non-binary and more oriented toward expressive intent and musicality. However, implementing such a feature was beyond the scope of this iteration, especially given the technical and resource demands of building a large-scale, multi-user application.

Data collection potential. While MuSA was primarily designed as a pedagogical application, it also functions as a valuable data collection tool. Since MuSA is deployed on a server hosted by the MTG at Universitat Pompeu Fabra, all uploaded recordings are automatically stored (with users explicitly consenting to data collection before using the tool). Additionally, each recording is labeled by instrument (currently voice and violin), allowing MuSA to serve as a passive, labeled dataset for these instruments. These recordings, accessible to those with server permissions, could be repurposed for future music performance analysis or music information retrieval tasks requiring labeled instrumental data.

5.2 Conclusions

Ultimately, more studies are needed to determine whether tools like MuSA can achieve broad, sustainable impact and whether there is genuine long-term demand for them among musicians. Despite the limitations of the MuSA evaluation study, the subjective responses and the original request from the RCM suggest that non-real-time feedback tools are perceived as valuable for independent practice and represent a meaningful gap in the current ecosystem of TEL for music. By implementing feature-driven saliency analysis, MuSA provides musicians with targeted, interpretable insights without prescribing “correct” solutions. In doing so, it foregrounds performance intent and interpretive decision-making rather than rigid score adherence. The evaluation study suggests that intermediate learners may benefit the most from this kind of feedback, while advanced musicians could, in some cases, experience negative effects—an outcome consistent with the expertise reversal effect. This finding underscores the importance of tailoring TEL tools to the learner’s developmental stage, as emphasized by the TAD model.

At the same time, MuSA illustrates how technology can scaffold self-regulated practice by highlighting moments that merit reflection, thus supporting metacognitive growth over time. However, its current implementation is limited in scope: tempo analysis remains underdeveloped, vibrato and phonation saliency require refinement, and affect-driven approaches such as activity analysis have yet to be explored. Moreover, while its online delivery maximizes accessibility, challenges of data storage and scalability remain unresolved. These limitations are not necessarily weaknesses, but rather opportunities for iterative design, refinement, and integration with other TEL approaches.

In parallel with these limitations, this project makes several constructive contributions. MuSA is not only a proof of concept but also a functioning, integrated testing platform that can be repurposed for future research. It simultaneously serves as a tool for delivering feedback, a framework for exploring the concept of saliency analysis, and a means of collecting performance data at scale. These features make it

a flexible resource that extends beyond the scope of this study and open possibilities for subsequent investigations. In this way, the platform itself represents an important outcome of the work, offering usable functionality and a foundation for subsequent work.

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Appendix A

Appendix: MuSA Evaluation Study Results

Table 4: Two-way ANOVA results for Raw RMSE performance (Condition \times Timing).

Source	Sum Sq	df	F	p-value
Condition	16139.20	1	1.44	0.2327 (ns)
Timing	4334.56	1	0.39	0.5356 (ns)
Condition \times Timing	4651.29	1	0.41	0.5211 (ns)
Residual	1686301.0	150		

Table 5: Group means and effect sizes (Cohen’s d) for RMSE performance. Significance: ** $p < 0.01$.

Feature n(Feedback)	Comparison	Mean Diff	Cohen’s d	p-value	Sig.	n(Before)	n(After)	n(Control)
Pitch –	After vs Before	-31.44	-0.21	0.4412	ns	28	28	–
Pitch 28	Feedback vs Control	40.40	0.27	0.3223	ns	–	–	28
Dynamics –	After vs Before	-0.0013	-0.04	0.8692	ns	28	28	–
Dynamics 28	Feedback vs Control	-0.0049	-0.17	0.5284	ns	–	–	28
Tempo –	After vs Before	6.18	0.36	0.2383	ns	20	22	–
Tempo 19	Feedback vs Control	15.07	0.97	0.0096	**	–	–	23

Table 6: Pitch (Hz) RMSE comparisons by experience level.

Experience n(Feedback)	Comparison	Mean Diff	Cohen's d	p-value	Sig.	n(Before)	n(After)	n(Control)
Beginner –	After vs Before	4.42	0.50	0.7046	ns	2	2	–
Beginner 2	Feedback vs Control	10.10	1.63	0.3272	ns	–	–	2
Intermediate –	After vs Before	-77.05	-0.37	0.3449	ns	14	14	–
Intermediate 14	Feedback vs Control	93.03	0.45	0.2539	ns	–	–	14
Advanced –	After vs Before	14.65	0.33	0.4705	ns	10	10	–
Advanced 10	Feedback vs Control	-20.13	-0.46	0.3190	ns	–	–	10
Professional –	After vs Before	21.53	1.37	0.3256	ns	2	2	–
Professional 2	Feedback vs Control	4.89	0.23	0.8585	ns	–	–	2

Table 7: Dynamics (RMS) RMSE comparisons by experience level.

Experience n(Feedback)	Comparison	Mean Diff	Cohen's d	p-value	Sig.	n(Before)	n(After)	n(Control)
Beginner –	After vs Before	-0.0055	-0.19	0.8686	ns	2	2	–
Beginner 2	Feedback vs Control	0.0409	7.58	0.0834	ns	–	–	2
Intermediate –	After vs Before	0.0038	0.15	0.7036	ns	14	14	–
Intermediate 14	Feedback vs Control	-0.0100	-0.39	0.3170	ns	–	–	14
Advanced –	After vs Before	-0.0048	-0.16	0.7172	ns	10	10	–
Advanced 10	Feedback vs Control	-0.0137	-0.48	0.3017	ns	–	–	10
Professional –	After vs Before	-0.0153	-0.76	0.5275	ns	2	2	–
Professional 2	Feedback vs Control	0.0284	2.62	0.1240	ns	–	–	2

Table 8: Tempo (BPM) RMSE comparisons by experience level.

Experience n(Feedback)	Comparison	Mean Diff	Cohen's d	p-value	Sig.	n(Before)	n(After)	n(Control)
Beginner –	After vs Before	25.10	0.86	0.5371	ns	2	2	–
Beginner 2	Feedback vs Control	35.30	1.50	0.3719	ns	–	–	2
Intermediate –	After vs Before	5.71	0.38	0.3577	ns	10	12	–
Intermediate 9	Feedback vs Control	12.98	0.94	0.0936	ns	–	–	13
Advanced –	After vs Before	9.54	0.59	0.3719	ns	7	6	–
Advanced 6	Feedback vs Control	10.58	0.66	0.3203	ns	–	–	7
Professional –	After vs Before	—	—	—	ns	–	–	–
Professional –	Feedback vs Control	—	—	—	ns	–	–	–

Table 9: Overall baseline-corrected RMSE improvements comparing feedback and control conditions. Cohen’s d and p -values indicate nonsignificant differences.

Feature	Control Mean	Feedback Mean	Difference	Cohen’s d	p -value	N Control	N Feedback
Pitch	-7.361	-17.485	-10.124	0.162	0.672	14	14
Dynamics	-8.304	5.790	14.094	0.409	0.289	14	14
Tempo	-53.474	-163.771	-110.297	0.431	1.000	9	7

Table 10: Baseline-corrected RMSE improvements (%) for pitch, dynamics, and tempo by musician experience level. Positive values indicate an advantage for the feedback condition; all comparisons were nonsignificant.

Experience Level	Pitch (%)	Dynamics (%)	Tempo (%)
Beginner	26.2 (p = nan)	9.2 (p = nan)	-181.5 (p = nan)
Intermediate	2.9 (p = 0.894)	27.1 (p = 0.176)	116.7 (p = 0.339)
Advanced	-28.5 (p = 0.639)	0.3 (p = 0.991)	-392.0 (p = 0.381)
Professional	-45.3 (p = nan)	-3.1 (p = nan)	—

Table 11: Overall Z-Score Standardized Improvement: Control vs Feedback

Feature	Mean Control	Mean Feedback	Difference	Cohen’s d	p -value	N Control	N Feedback
Pitch	0.082	-0.082	-0.165	-0.162	0.674	14	14
Dynamics	-0.204	0.204	0.408	0.409	0.289	14	14
Tempo	0.190	-0.244	-0.434	-0.431	1.000	9	7

Table 12: Z-Score Standardized Improvement by Experience Level: Control vs Feedback

Feature	Experience	Mean Control	Mean Feedback	Difference	Cohen’s d	p -value	N Control	N Feedback
Pitch	Intermediate	0.280	0.327	0.047	0.072	0.896	7	7
Pitch	Advanced	-0.172	-0.636	-0.464	-0.308	0.841	5	5
Dynamics	Intermediate	-0.537	0.248	0.784	0.769	0.187	7	7
Dynamics	Advanced	0.050	0.059	0.009	0.008	0.991	5	5
Tempo	Intermediate	0.081	0.540	0.460	0.848	0.286	6	2
Tempo	Advanced	0.584	-0.960	-1.544	-0.935	0.316	2	3

Table 13: Overall Perceived Performance Ratings by Condition. Significance: * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Feature	Condition	Before (Mean \pm SD)	After (Mean \pm SD)	Δ	t	p -value	Cohen’s d	Sig.
Pitch	Control	5.07 \pm 0.92	5.29 \pm 0.99	+0.22	-1.148	0.274	-0.122	ns
Pitch	Feedback	5.15 \pm 1.57	5.36 \pm 0.84	+0.21	-0.457	0.656	-0.122	ns
Dynamics	Control	4.14 \pm 1.46	4.57 \pm 1.22	+0.43	-1.031	0.321	—	ns
Dynamics	Feedback	4.07 \pm 1.07	5.07 \pm 0.92	+1.00	-4.266	0.0009	-1.003	***
Tempo	Control	3.92 \pm 1.62	4.86 \pm 1.29	+0.94	-3.071	0.011	-0.563	*
Tempo	Feedback	4.00 \pm 1.22	4.64 \pm 0.74	+0.64	-1.865	0.089	—	ns

Table 14: Perceived Performance Improvement ($\Delta = \text{After} - \text{Before}$) with t-statistics and p-values by Experience Level and Condition.

Feature	Experience	Control (Δ)	Feedback (Δ)	t-statistic	p-value
Pitch	Beginner	+1.00	-1.00	—	—
Pitch	Intermediate	+0.29	+0.14	-0.281	0.7882
Pitch	Advanced	+0.00	+0.60	—	—
Pitch	Professional	+0.00	+0.00	—	—
Dynamics	Beginner	-2.00	+2.00	—	—
Dynamics	Intermediate	+1.43	+1.29	-6.971	0.0004
Dynamics	Advanced	-0.40	+0.40	-0.784	0.4766
Dynamics	Professional	+0.00	+1.00	—	—
Tempo	Beginner	+3.00	+1.00	—	—
Tempo	Intermediate	+1.33	+1.05	0.000	1.0000
Tempo	Advanced	+0.20	+0.00	0.000	1.0000
Tempo	Professional	—	+1.00	—	—

Table 15: Correlation Analysis of Self-Assessment Accuracy by Feature

Feature	Corr. (r)	p-value	Interpretation	Sample Size	Overconfident	Underconfident
Pitch	-0.111	0.599	Poor self-awareness	27	1	2
Dynamics	-0.080	0.683	Poor self-awareness	28	2	2
Tempo	-0.078	0.787	Poor self-awareness	15	2	0

Table 16: Self-Awareness Comparison: Control vs Feedback Conditions

Feature / Metric	Control r	Control Error (M \pm SD)	Control n	Feedback r	Feedback Error (M \pm SD)	Feedback n	Condition Comparison p
Overall	-0.027	4.03 \pm 6.17	36	-0.182	7.16 \pm 16.96	34	0.738 [†] / 0.303 [*]
Pitch	0.089	1.87	14	-0.160	5.02	13	0.062
Dynamics	-0.267	3.38	14	0.101	2.29	14	0.148
Tempo	0.317	8.96	8	-0.363	20.88	7	0.694

Note. [†] Mann-Whitney U test; ^{*} independent t-test. Absolute self-awareness error: lower values indicate better alignment between perceived and actual performance.

Table 17: Self-Awareness by Musical Experience Level (Correlation with Objective Performance)

Experience Level	r	n (assessments)	p-value	Interpretation
Beginner	-0.293	6	0.57	Not significant (limited data)
Intermediate	0.244	35	0.16	Not significant
Advanced	-0.437	24	0.033	Significant (inverse awareness)
Professional	0.694	5	0.19	Not significant (limited data)

Table 18: Representative participant quotes by question and sentiment.

Question	Sentiment	Quote
Experience	Positive	(n7oh8onc) It was good! It definitely was better than just plain practice. I liked the highlighted regions where it detected potential inconsistencies.
Experience	Positive	(ndrqs3sg) I think that the feedback is useful for engagement and increase the desire of improvement. It could be useful, at some point that you have the graphics and try to adjust to them in real time.
Experience	Negative	(chxrj0wq) The feedback tool was not in real-time so I could not make immediate corrections. It was not very easy to adjust my pitch after the analysis tool. The feedback tool was useful in understanding where I was correct and whe...
Experience	Negative	(y6v3g63s) The tool looks great but seems to have some problem with alignments between what I sang and what was supposed to be sang.
Improvement	Positive	(y6v3g63s) For sure!
Improvement	Positive	(b068bafw) Yes, I focused more on nuances, the hardest one was tempo because I didn't know if I was rushing or not.
Improvement	Negative	(oplv7i5e) Not really because for me auditory cues are more helpful than visual cues.
Improvement	Negative	(3d1ly0bg) It's hard to say, I hope there's a control group that is just practicing and listening to their own audio, because I feel like the practice inherently helps.
Highlights	Positive	(w4m19emj) Yes they were helpful for showing me where I need to focus.
Highlights	Positive	(xzdbn2c2) Yes definitely. The pitch curve and dynamics curve were quite good choices for the plot.
Highlights	Negative	(3tzisfce) They were, but sometimes I wouldn't see any highlighted area even though I still considered the performance not perfect at all.
Highlights	Negative	(3d1ly0bg) Yeah they were.
Payment	Positive	(etuygx3k) If I were recording music I would definitely pay for it because I think it is very useful for improving but at the moment I don't have a need for it.
Payment	Positive	(ndrqs3sg) If my work implied singing, yes, but I would compare it first to other similar tools if exists. If singing is a hobby I would not pay for it.
Payment	Negative	(w4m19emj) I would pay a maximum of 5\$ a month.
Payment	Negative	(oplv7i5e) No.

Table 19: Summary of sentiment analysis results, including overall statistics, per-question means and medians, and correlation between lexicon and VADER sentiment.

Category	Sentiment	Mean	Median	N / Notes
<i>Overall Sentiment Statistics</i>				
Overall	Lexicon	0.223	0.200	56
Overall	VADER	0.370	0.458	56
<i>Sentiment by Question</i>				
Experience	Lexicon	0.308	0.306	14
Experience	VADER	0.671	0.795	14
Improvement	Lexicon	0.186	0.191	14
Improvement	VADER	0.286	0.402	14
Highlights	Lexicon	0.242	0.200	14
Highlights	VADER	0.282	0.421	14
Payment	Lexicon	0.156	0.000	14
Payment	VADER	0.241	0.095	14
<i>Correlation</i>				
Lexicon vs VADER	Pearson r	0.549	—	—